

The path of the “history” of Art. 2 TEU, its collocation with other articles of the Treaty of Lisbon and its use in the Court of Justice of the European Union

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The path of the “history” of Art. 2 TEU, its collocation with other articles of the Treaty of Lisbon and its use in the Court of Justice of the European Union

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Abstract:The present paper has tried to investigate and give answers, statements and analyze the doubts related to Art. 2 TEU. However, the way is difficult given that Art. 2 TEU is connected with several articles of the CFREU but also with Art. 7 TEU. The theories are varied but what helps us to understand and better analyze and understand the values of the EU is the jurisprudence of the CJEU. Substantive profiles that lead us to analyze a variety of arguments and themes such as the European arrest warrant, the right to expression, the principle of democracy, etc. But also to answer certain questions, i.e. What are the jurisdictional remedies of Art. 2 TEU? What types of appeals can it makes? What articles can be included with it? Can it alone be a subject of litigation and be presented before the CJEU? These are some of the topics discussed in our survey.

Keywords: Art. 2 TEU; Art. 7 TEU; Art. 19, TEU; Art. 47 CFREU; European Union law; rule of law; CJEU; values of the EU.

What are the founding values of the Union?

The deep roots and identity of the European Union are outlined and find their basis of expression in Art. 2 TEU which was introduced by the Treaty of Lisbon (Liakopoulos, 2019b). This paper does not aim to speak generally of Art. 2 TEU (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). It is based on the values on which the Union is founded, i.e. the common values of the Member States which evoke and flourish the life of the “common society” (Gesellschaft Gemeinsam) of the Union and of its Member States (Hatje, Terhechte, Müller -Graff, 2018; Liakopoulos, 2019b; Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019; Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019; Schwarze, Becker, Hatje, Schoo, 2019; Spieker, 2021)¹ as well as the values of an ethical nature (Frischhut, 2022).

What are these values? Values of human dignity, freedom, equality, rule of law, democracy, as well as respect for human rights especially those of minorities that listed in the first part of

¹We mention that the values listed in the second sentence of article 2 of the TEU are also mentioned, namely “pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men”, more generally, in the preamble of the CFREU. These values are inspired by Articles 8-12 of the ECHR.

Art. 2 TEU and in the preamble of the same treaty which can be defined as “fundamental”, i.e a list of rights which are also part of the title I TEU (Liakopoulos, 2018c; Spieker, 2021)². These are the values that the EU is based on, but also on Art. 49 TEU one of the main elements for each candidate European State to be part of the European family (Liakopoulos, 2019b)³. It is a prerequisite that we encountered in the distant European Council of 1993 and after being referred to in the Madrid Council of 1995. It is called the Copenhagen criteria and are related to:

“(...) the presence of stable institutions which guarantee a democratic system (Isiksel, 2016; Lyn Entrikin, 2019), the rule of law, human rights, respect for minorities and their protection (...)” (Voeneky, Neuman, 2018; Pech, 2022), as a representation of a necessary condition to start negotiations for accession to the Union (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019).

In the recent Wightman judgment, the CJEU underlined the importance of the values of freedom and democracy, which are among the common values of article 2 TEU, and which in this sense form part of the very foundations of the Union legal order as it appears from article 49 of the TEU (Haratsch, Koenig, Pechstein, 2020) according to which any European state can

²In accordance with the TEU preamble, Member States confirm “(...) their attachment to the principles of freedom, democracy and respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms and the rule of law (...)”.

³“(...) there is no denying the founding nature of values based on the fact that these values were not mentioned in the original version of the Treaty of Rome, which listed the four basic freedoms, agriculture and transport, among the "bases" of the Community. The only “European” state condition was sufficient to apply for membership. The European Union is a much more ambitious project than the original EEC, and this is what the Lisbon Treaty refers to art. 8. Previously, in 1984, the Spinelli Project (article 2) provided that “any democratic European state” could apply to become a member of the Union (...)”.

apply to become a member of the Union but also using article 50 TEU to request its withdrawal from it. The Union brings together states that have freely and voluntarily adhered to these values (Liakopoulos, 2019a)⁴. The importance of the affirmations of the judges of Luxembourg make us understand that Art. 2 TEU is important and stands above all other treaty provisions. Its importance and “superiority” is also underlined by the CJEU in Opinion 2/13 (Lock, 2010; Potteau, 2011; Kuijer, 2011; Ladenburger, 2011; Jacquè, 2011; O’Meara, 2011; Ashiagbor, Countouris, Lianos, 2012; Polakiewicz, 2013; Janssens, 2013; Torres Perez, 2013; De Witte, 2014; Meyer, 2014; Halbestram, 2015; Peers, 2015; Krenn, 2015; Lambrecht, 2015; Petite, 2015; Spaventa, 2015; Halleslov Storgaard, 2015; Korenica, 2015; Morano-Foadi, Vickers, 2015; Lock, 2015; Picod, 2015; Wesse, Łazowski, 2015; Billing, 2016; Liakopoulos, 2018)⁵.

⁴CJEU, C-621/18 Wightman et al., of 10 December 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:999, not published, par. 62-63.

⁵Opinion 2/13, Accession of the European Union to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, ECJ, 18 December 2014, ECLI:EU:C:2014:2454. According to Halleslov Storgaard: “(...) on the one hand, the art. 53 does not oblige the states to guarantee a higher level of protection than that of the ECHR, on the other the same CFREU must guarantee the same level of protection of the ECHR so that there is no conflict between the two provisions. Moreover, the CJEU has evoked the specificity of the Union’s control system on respect for fundamental rights, in particular the principle of mutual trust in the areas of civil and criminal judicial cooperation, visa, asylum and immigration, namely the area of freedom, security and justice that obliges each member state to presume respect for fundamental rights by the other member states and the absence of their jurisdictional powers in the field of foreign and security policy. See also in case: C-168/13 PPU, Jeremy F. of 30 May 2013, ECLI:EU:C:2013:358, published in the electronic Reports

The CJEU repeated in other words the old pivotal judgment *Van Gend & Loos* (Stein, 1981; Weiler, 1991; Vauchez, 2010; Rasmussen, 2014; Rodin, Perišin, 2015; Sankari, 2016; Maduro, 2017; Barnard, peers, 2017; Conway, 2017; Lindseth, 2018; Usherwood, Pinder, 2018; Rasmussen, Martinsen, 2019)⁶ stating that the Union is endowed with a legal order of a new kind, having its own specific nature, a constitutional framework and founding principles that belong to it, a particularly elaborate institutional structure, as well as a complete set of legal rules that guarantee its functioning (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019). It has created a structured network of mutually interdependent principles, rules and legal relationships, which bind, in a reciprocal way, the Union itself and its Member States, as well as, between them, the Member States (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019). Such a legal construction rests on the fundamental premise that each Member State shares with all

of the cases. The CJEU affirmed that: “(...) the absence of the necessary provisions of the Framework it frameworks, it must be that the framework for the implementation of the objectives of the framework to a European Arrest Warrant (...)”. In the same spirit see also. CJEU, C-399/11, *Stefano Melloni* of 26 February 2013, ECLI:EU:C:2013:107; C-396/11, *Ministerul Public-Parchetul de pe lângă Curtea de Apel Constanța v. Radu* of 29 January 2013, ECLI:EU:C:2013:39, both of them published in the electronic Reports of the cases.

⁶CJEU, C-26/62, *Van Gend & Loos v. Amministrazione olandese delle imposte* of 5 February 1963, ECLI:EU:C:1963:1, I-00003. C-56/65, *Technique Minière* of 30 June 1966, ECLI:EU:C:1966:38, I-00337. C-43/71, *Politi* of 14 December 1971, ECLI:EU:C:1971:122, I-01039. joined cases C-162 and 258/85, *Pugnaloni* of 12 June 1986, ECLI:EU:C:1986:246, I-01885. C-267/86, *Van Eicke/ASPA* of 21 September 1988, ECLI:EU:C:1988:427, I-04769. Rasmussen: calling the constitutionalization of the Treaty a “decisive turning point in the history of the European Court of Justice and of EU law in general.

other Member States, and recognizes that

“they share with it, a set of common values on which the Union is founded, as specified in article 2 TEU. This premise implies and justifies the existence of mutual trust between the Member States as regards the recognition of these values and, therefore, respect for the Union law which implements them (...)” (Nicola, Davies, 2017).

Immediately from the first statements of the CJEU and the same wording of Art. 2 TEU we can understand that it is an article that identifies the constitutional principle of the EU. Opinion 1/17 is equally important, where the CJEU affirms that the Union has its own constitutional framework which includes the founding values set out in article 2 TEU (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019), i.e. the general principles of the law of Union, the provisions of the Charter of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFREU), in particular the provisions of the treaties, the rules on the attribution and division of powers, the rules for the functioning of the institutions of the Union and the system jurisdiction of the same, as well as key standards in specific sectors, structured to contribute to the completion of the integration process referred to in Article 1, second paragraph, TEU (Reffel, 2019; Iorio, 2019; Eckes, 2020; Cremona, 2020)⁷.

Art. 2 TEU is addressed to both the institutions of the EU and the Member States. On the one hand, the Institutions are required to respect this article (Barents, 2020; Eckes, 2020)⁸,

⁷CJEU, Opinion 1/17 of 30 April 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:341, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 110.

⁸CJEU, C-620/16, Commission v. Germany of 27 March 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:256, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 50: “Moreover, to admit the inadmissibility of an action for failure to fulfill obligations

given that it is the first to enter into the objectives of the Union according to Art. 3, par. 1 TEU for the promotion of peace, its values and the well-being of its peoples and on the other to turn to the external action of the Union (Corthaut, 2012; Guinchard, Granger, 2016; Liakopoulos, 2019b; Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019)⁹ as identified and specified in the related articles 13, 21 and 42, par. 5 TEU (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021).

Art. 2 TEU is also addressed to the Member States specifying the values which are:

“common to the Member States in a society characterized by pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men”¹⁰.

This observation affirms the general nature which connects with the fate of the Member States and also functions as a barrier line for the candidate states for the EU. The CJEU has already

against a Member State on account of a breach of a decision adopted pursuant to Article 218 (9) TFEU would be prejudicial both to the mandatory nature of the decisions pursuant to of the fourth paragraph of Article 288 TFEU, both in general and for the respect of the values on which the Union is founded”, pursuant to Article 2 TEU, which include, in particular, the “rule of law” or in relation to the principle of legality (sentence Dzivev). See also the conclusions of the Advocate General Kokott in case: C-561/16 *Saras Energía* of 12 April 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:236, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 75: “However, the obligation to state reasons has its roots in the rule of law principle, which is common to all Member States pursuant to Article 2 TEU and is also the basis of the Union (...)”.

9CJEU, C-355/04, *Segi and other v. Council* of 27 February 2008, ECLI:EU:C:2007:116, I-01657, par. 51. C-455/14-P, *H v. Council and Commission* of 19 July 2016, ECLI:EU:C:2016:569, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 41. C-72/15 *Rosneft* of 28 March 2017, ECLI:EU:C:2017:236, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 72.

10In accordance with the preamble to the TEU, states are inspired by the “cultural, religious and humanistic heritage of Europe, from which the universal values that constitute the inviolable and inalienable rights of the human person are developed, as well as freedom, democracy, equality and state of right”.

reaffirmed this position recognizing it as a fundamental premise that each Member State shares for all the other Member States, i.e. recognizing Art. 2 TEU as a provision that creates obligations for a Member State both towards the Union and towards the other Member States.

The connection of Art. 2 TEU with the procedures of Art. 7 TEU, para. 1 and 3 is a confirmation of the violation of the principles established by the same article and the procedures foreseen (Halmak, 2018; Breuer, 2019; Jakab, Kochenov, 2017; Liakopoulos, 2019b; Schmahl, 2019; Oates, 2020; Neuwahl, Kovacs, 2020; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). This is an obvious early warning mechanism for a serious violation by a Member State of the values of Art. 2 TEU. This is the ascertainment of a serious and persistent violation of these values by a Member State and its suspension through the right to vote by the other Member States. The connection of Art. 2 TEU with the provision of such severe and exceptional sanctions highlights the constitutional importance of this type of values. Art. 2 TEU contains in itself a binding force that can be invoked in a case law dispute. Overall, Art. 2 TEU but also the other provisions of the treaties and the relevant jurisprudence up to now are quite rich and pave the way for various interpretations, comments and evaluations which are subjects of open debate also for the years to come.

The relationship of Articles 4 and 2 TEU

The question that rises up at this point is the relationship between Articles 2 and 4 TEU and especially if Art. 4 TEU¹¹ is able to somehow constitute an exception to the first (Davies, Aubelj, 2018; Antal, 2019; Mader, 2019; Kelemen, Pech, 2019). According to some scholars Art. 4, par. 3 TEU is configured as a sort of specific clause which specifically authorizes the Member States for the purpose of asserting the related derogations from the common rules (Von Bogdandy, Schill, 2011; Constantindies, 2011; Saiz Arnaiz, Alcoberro Llivina, 2013; Toniatti, 2013; Blanke, Vilalàn, Klein, Ziller, 2016; Contiades, Fotiadou, 2016) respecting however the protection of one's national and sovereign identity (Nowag, 2017). According to others, the identity clause of Art. 4, par. 2 TEU cannot justify the violation of the values envisaged in Art. 2 TEU (Guastaffero, 2012; Duque, 2013; Dobbs, 2015; Faraguna, 2017; Di Federico, 2019; Liakopoulos, 2019b, Calliess, Van Der Schyff, 2019; Spieker, 2020)¹².

¹¹See the conclusions of the Advocate General Nicholas Emiliou in case: C-391/20, Cilevičs and others of 08 March 2022, ECLI:EU:C:2022:166, not yet published, par. 83 “(...) the nature of Article 4(2) TEU, it seems to me that that provision has, first and foremost, a dual nature. On the one hand, it requires the EU legislature to take into account Member States’ national identities when adopting legislation. Logically, a similar obligation must exist in respect of all EU institutions and bodies when they adopt other legally binding acts. In that respect, national identity may thus function also as a parameter of validity: any EU act that would irredeemably conflict with the national identity of one or more Member States would be invalid for a breach of Article 4(2) TEU (...)”.

¹²According to Spieker: “(...) as long as the Member States are part of the Union,

If it allows us to speak of an identity clause we can also justify violations of Art. 2 TEU which contrast the founding, constitutional and supreme nature of the related values affirmed in this article. In our opinion and based on a systematic interpretation of Art. 4, par. 2, the same article also includes other principles and provisions which are based on Art. 6 TEU (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019). This statement makes us understand that the identity clause must be investigated not separately but according to other principles which are based on Art. 4 TEU (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021) and are related to the attribution and equality of the Member States before the related treaties that speak for a sincere cooperation (Klamert, 2014; Neframi, 2015). These principles, even very different from each other, are linked and interpreted together.

Article 2 TEU defines a common constitutional identity from which they cannot derogate. Such an understanding is not only indicated by the wording of Article 2 TEU, but also by Articles 7 and 49(1) TEU. This obligation also extends to the Member States' constitutional or national identities under Article 4(2) TEU, which may not contradict the Union's values (...)"

Already the first paragraph of Art. 4 TEU affirms the principle of attribution as well as the provisions included in the Treaty of Lisbon¹³. This principle requires the relative respect of the competences of the Member States together with the principle of sincere cooperation and as a source of the relative obligations of the Member States which must respect the competences attributed to the Union.

As regards the second paragraph of Art. 4 TEU, respect for the national identity of the Member States (Perju, 2019) and the principle of equality find affirmation in the treaties (Rossi, 2017). This principle has been used by CJEU as a type of brake before the granting of the relative derogations from the common rules and above all from the transitional periods that are granted upon the entry of the new Member States (Craig, De Bùrca, 2011)¹⁴ as a measure of justification to different and new Member States that find themselves in similar situations

¹³The principle of attribution is mentioned in Articles 4.1, 5 TEU, Articles 2, protocol (n.21) of the Lisbon Treaty on the position of the United Kingdom and Ireland with respect to the area of freedom, and the judicial system, in Article 2, Protocol (No. 22) on the position of Denmark and in the Protocol (No. 30) on the application of the CFREU of fundamental rights of the European Union to Poland and the United Kingdom. It is also mentioned in the declarations (n.1) on the CFREU of fundamental rights, (n.13), on the common foreign and security policy, (n.18) on the delimitation of powers, (n.24) on the legal personality of the European Union, (No. 31) relating to the application of Article 156 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, (No. 42) relating to Article 352 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union and (No. 53) of the Czech Republic on the CFREU of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

¹⁴CJEU, C-231/78, Commission v. United Kingdom of 29 March 1979, ECLI:EU:C:1979:101, I-01447.

(Churchill, Owen, 2010; Lenaerts, Maselis, Gutman, 2014; Rosas, Armati, 2018)¹⁵. The most important debatable point remains the principle of equality which actually prohibits trying to obtain situations that are favorable to the detriment of others. In this spirit, the case *Commission v. Italy*, where it is stated that:

“(...) the fact that a state, in consideration of its own national interests, unilaterally breaks the balance between the advantages and burdens deriving from its membership of the community harms the equality of the Member States before the Community law and determines discrimination against their citizens (...) this failure to fulfill the duties of solidarity accepted by the Member States with their accession to the Community shakes the foundations of the Community legal order (...)”¹⁶.

It is permitted to say that in the case just mentioned a precise link can be glimpsed between the principle of equality and loyal cooperation and solidarity which refers to the global formulation of Art. 4 TEU¹⁷. Thus the identity clause is invoked that the states must respect the principle of attribution and all its corollaries such as for example that of the preemption and the related matters of a competitive nature. On the other hand, the states take into consideration the fact that the identity clause is configured as a type of exception to the relative rule of equality of the Member States before the law and must be interpreted

¹⁵CJEU, C-273/04, *Poland v. Council* of 23 October 2007, ECLI:EU:C:2007:622, I-08925. C-73/90, *Spain v. Council* of 13 October 1992, ECLI:EU:C:1992:384, I-5191.

¹⁶CJEU, C-39/72, *Commission v. Italy* of 17 February 1973, ECLI:EU:C:1973:13, I-00101.

¹⁷CJEU, C-13/63, *Italy c. Commission* of 17 July 1963, ECLI:EU:C:1963:20, I-00165. C-203/86, *Kingdom of Spain v. Council of European Communities* of 20 September 1988, ECLI:EU:C:1988:420, I-04563.

restrictively before the European institutions which have the obligation to apply it. National identity thus finds a limit in the principle of loyal cooperation (Kochenov, 2012; Roes, 2016; Vogenauer, Weatherill, 2017; Cremona, 2018; Casolari, 2020), as based on Art. 4, lit. 4 TEU (Kumm, 2005; Arigho, 2014; Kelemen, Pech, 2018; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). A principle already affirmed in the past by the Treaty of Rome (Stein, 1981; Boerger-De Smedt, 2012; Bernier, 2012)¹⁸ and used many times by the CJEU in combination with other provisions of the treaty or alone (Bitter, 2002; Rodin, 2011; Bruun, Lörcher, Schömann, 2012; Broberg, Fenger, 2013; Martinico, 2013; Roccati, 2014; Planzer, 2014; Koutrakos, Nic Schuibhne, Syrpis, 2016; Barav, 2017; Kelemen, Pech, 2018; Abazi, 2019; Davies, 2019)¹⁹. By

¹⁸Boerger-De Smedt arguing that “(...) a small number of politicians and jurists managed to insert the potential for constitutional practice into the treaties despite the conscious attempt by the majority of the governments not to establish a European constitutional order (...) it is worth remembering that, in the large majority of cases, subsequent treaties ratified the decisions of the court by incorporating them into the text of the revised treaties (...)”. According to Stein: “(...) Tucked away in the fairyland Duchy of Luxembourg and blessed, until recently, with benign neglect by the powers that be and the mass media, the Court of Justice of the European Communities has fashioned a constitutional framework for a federal-type structure (...)”.

¹⁹CJEU, C-340/89, Vlassopoulou of 7 May 1991, ECLI:EU:C:1991:193, I-02357. C-238/98, Hoesman of 14 September 2000, ECLI:EU:C:2000:440, I-06623. C-213/89, Factortame of 19 June 1990, ECLI:EU:C:1990:257, I-02433. C-409/06, Winner Wetten GmbH v. Bürgermeisterin der Stadt Bergheim of 8 September 2010, ECLI:EU:C:2010:503, I-08015. C-515/08, dos Santos Palhota and others of 7 October 2010, ECLI:EU:C:2010:589, I-09133. The Advocate General Villalon argued that values listed in Art. 9 TFEU (high level of employment, adequate social protection, high level of education) are ground for greater discretion to Member States. Interpreting AG Villalon’s position to mean that: “(...) a high level of social protection constitutes part of the national identity of Member States and justifies a departure from market freedoms (...)”. The Court did not follow the AG’s recommendations. C-173/09, Georgi Ivanov Elchinov v. Natsionalna zdravnoosiguritelna kasa of 5 October 2010, ECLI:EU:C:2010:581, I-08889.

carefully reading these articles we can focus on the obligation of sincere cooperation (Klamert, 2014; Neframi, 2015). Respect for the equality of Member States and for their own identity as well as the principle of attribution as an integral part of the relevant principle of sincere cooperation with the Union.

We recall the principle of loyal cooperation in the Achmea case (Biondi, Birkinshaw, Kendrick, 2018; Nagy, 2019; Soloch, 2019; Monsenego, 2019)²⁰. It makes us think that the right of the Union is based on a fundamental premise that each Member State shares with all the other Member States and the related values of article 2 TEU, as a premise which implies, justifies the existence of a trust of nature between the Member States in their recognition of these values, where the same CJEU already notes that:

“(...) it is precisely in this context that it is up to the Member States, in particular, by virtue of the principle of sincere cooperation, enshrined in article 4, paragraph 3, first subparagraph, TEU, the duty to guarantee, in their respective territories, the application of and compliance with Union law and to adopt, for these purposes, any general or specific measure capable of guaranteeing the fulfillment of the obligations deriving from treaties or acts of the institutions of the Union (...)” (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019).

On the one hand, the reference to Art. 4, par. 2 TEU defines the structural identity of the Member States according to the principles of a structural nature of the territorial protection of the related national constitutional systems, given that the same

²⁰CJEU, C-284/16 Slowakische Republik v. Achmea BV of 6 March 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:158, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 34.

article states that:

“The Union respects (...) the national identity of the Member States inherent in their fundamental political and constitutional structure, including the system of local and regional self-government. It respects the essential functions of the state, in particular the functions of safeguarding territorial integrity, maintaining public order and protecting national security (...)” (Liakopoulos, 2019b).

The article also comes to speak for national security which remains to the exclusive competence of each state. Each Member State has the power to define what are its “fundamental political and constitutional structures” (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019), as they are referred to and identified through Article 4, paragraph 2, TEU which speaks to us, *rectius* refers to the division of competences within the federal states, as well as to the distribution of these competences between the state and the regions and to the organization of the related institutional structures, the form of government and the “essential functions” of the state including security, defense and services of general interest where the treaty of Lisbon devotes particular attention.

Greater attention is given to a complex and multilevel system which is composed by Art. 6 of the Charter of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFREU) and from the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) (Grabenwarter, Pabel, 2021; Sudre, 2021; Villiger, 2023), as well as from the common constitutional traditions of the Member States. Thus the fundamental rights which are affirmed by the Constitutions of the Member States are considered by the various “national

identities” which find their basis in Art. 4, par. 2 TEU, Art. 2 TEU, Art. 6, par. 3 TEU and Articles 52, par. 4 and 53 CFREU (Stern, Sachs, 2016; Picod, Van Droogbenbroeck, 2018; Picod, Van Droogbenbroeck, 2018; Pila, Torremans, 2019; Dorssemont, Lörcher, Clauwaert, 2019; Haratsch, Koenig, Pechstein, 2020; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021)²¹. The common constitutional traditions have an autonomous character created and used by the CJEU itself even before they are integrated into the primary law of the treaty of Maastricht. We cannot find such a concept in the constitutional courts of the Member States, but in the CJEU which clarifies when a constitutional tradition becomes “common” within the legal framework of the Union, i.e. a general principle which is verified by a constitution through a derogation from the application of the law of the Union (Liakopoulos, 2019b)²². Each Member State has the possibility to derogate from the provisions of the law of the Union thus invoking the relevant fundamental rights deriving

²¹See also Article 67.1 TFEU, which, taking into account the area of freedom, security and justice, provides “respect for fundamental rights and the different legal systems and traditions of the Member States (...)”.

²²“(...) common constitutional traditions are an open category, developed by the Court not on the basis of simple comparative analyzes, and even less looking for a lower common denominator among the traditions. On the contrary, the Court examined whether the values invoked by the Member State as justification for the derogation from Union rules deserve to be considered common, also in the light of the other general principles of the Union, thus becoming precisely for the latter an internal source of general principles of law. The role of the norms foreseen by the various national Constitutions, referred to in Article 53 of the CFREU, is however distinct, in that they nevertheless represent values “external” to the legal order of the Union and which must however be compared with the principles of primacy and the autonomy of the legal order of the European Union (...)”.

from the relevant provisions, constitutional, national traditions which are subject to strict control by the CJEU (Fichera, 2018; Chalmers, Davies, Monti, 2019)²³. The Member States are here to respect fundamental rights as a clause not only for entry into the European family but also for continuous respect for the large family they belong to according to the principles of Art. 2 TEU of a systemic nature and by the CFREU applicable to secondary legislation of the EU, such as an identity clause justifying infringements of article 2 TEU which are committed by a Member State.

Article 2 TEU and 19, para. 1 TEU. Independence of national judgments

Already since 2017 with the Rosneft case the CJEU has tried to declare the existence of a judicial control which is intended to guarantee respect for the law of the Union (Liakopoulos, 2018c; Liakopoulos, 2022; Pech, 2022) which in this case is understood substantially and coinciding with the protection of human rights by evoking the existence of a legal system which is equipped with a mechanism for respecting a relative hierarchy (Lenaerts, 2015; De Baere, Roes, 2015; Küris, 2018; Wouters, Rynbgaert, Ruys, De Baere, 2018).

²³CJEU, C-438/14 Nabil Peter Bogendorff von Wolffersdorff of 2 June 2016, ECLI:EU:C:2016:401, published in the electronic Reports of the cases. C-208/09, Sayn-Wittgenstein of 22 December 2010, ECLI:EU:C:2010:806, I-13693.

Continuing with the *Associação Sindical dos Juizes Portugueses* case (Varju, 2019)²⁴, the CJEU has taken a position in relation to Art. 19, par. 1, lit. 2 TEU, where:

“(…) it embodies the value of the rule of law affirmed in article 2 TEU (…) common to the Member States in a society characterized, in particular, by justice (…)” (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). The CJEU has declared, by virtue of the principle of loyal cooperation, the duty to the Member States to guarantee the right established by Art. 4, par. 3 TEU as a judicial protection in the sectors that are covered by the law of the Union and providing for a system of remedies and procedures that guarantee the relative judicial control in these sectors (Varju, 2019). The connection with the provisions of the TEU is a clear, precise reference to the independence of national judges as a necessary element of the rule of law (Wendt, 2012)²⁵ and a simultaneous connection with respect for values according to Art. 2 TEU in relation to the trust in which they are based under the area of freedom, security and justice and especially in the area of the European Arrest Warrant (Liakopoulos, 2012; Liakopoulos, 2018a; Liakopoulos, 2019b). It distinguishes the

²⁴CJEU, C-64/16 *Associação Sindical dos Juizes Portugueses* of 27 February 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:117, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 30. In the same spirit see also: C-216/18 PPU, *Minister for Justice and Equality* of 25 July 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:586, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 50ss.

²⁵CJEU, T-51/89, *Tetra Pak Rausing SA v. Commission of the European Communities* of 10 July 1990, ECLI:EU:T:1990:41, II-00309, par. 40: “(…) [W]hen applying [Community law], the national courts are acting as Community courts of general jurisdiction (…)”.

relationship between the relations of the Union and its Member States which concerns the relations between the Member States and their own national authorities. The link between Articles 2 and 19 TEU gives a new dimension to the horizon in relation to the concept of independence of national judgments while respecting at the same time Articles 267 TFEU (Schwarze, Becker, Hatje, Schoo, 2019; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021) and 47 CFREU (Mak, 2012; Saffian, Düsterhau, 2014; Öhlinger, 2014; Lebrun, 2016). Perhaps it would be appropriate to recall the old leader case of *Simmenthal*, where it was stated that the judges of the Member States are also judges of the legal system of the European Union²⁶. One's independence is fundamental to this legal system and in various aspects above all to the concrete situations that come into play in a separate way and with the relative consequences of gradual intensity.

A relative independence also comes from Art. 267 TFEU (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019) in relation to national bodies as jurisdictions that have the power and duty to refer the related questions of a preliminary nature to the CJEU (Lenaerts, 2019). Already the CJEU states that a body

“(...) does not have the independence necessary to be qualified as a court within the meaning of article 267 TFEU, it limits itself to rejecting the question referred to it by that body (...)” (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019).

²⁶C-106/77, *Italian Minister of Finance v. Simmenthal* of 9 March 1978, ECLI:EU:C:1978:49, I-00629, parr. 16 and 38.

Mainly, the Member State is unable to modify the statute of this body and even more to abolish it. The character of “judicial body”, according to Art. 267 TFEU (Schwarze, Becker, Hatje, Schoo, 2019; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021) finds interpretation through the CJEU which actually tried to take into consideration a series of factors, such as the constitution by law of this body, its permanent nature, the mandatory nature of its jurisdiction and its procedure, as well as the power to apply the rules of law and its independence (Uzelac, Hendrik, Van Rhee, 2018; Chalmers, Davies, Monti, 2019)²⁷. Internal judges fall within the ambit of Art. 47 CFREU (Bobek, Adams Prassl, 2020; Jarass, 2020; Picod, Van Droogbenbroeck, 2020; Tinière, Vial, 2020; Peers and others, 2021; Ripol Carulla, Ligartemendia Uceizabarrena, 2022; Casarosa, Moraru, 2022). In the LM case the CJEU clarified that:

“(…) the presence of an independent and impartial judge constitutes both an essential element of a fair trial (…) and a subjective right, which Member States are required to guarantee to all defendants within the CFREU of fundamental rights (…)” (Granat, Granat, 2019; Lenaerts, Bonichot, Naômè, Pohjankowski, 2019; Varju, 2019)²⁸.

²⁷CJEU, C-61/65 Vaassen-Göbbels of 30 June 1966, ECLI:EU:C:1966:39, I-00261, par. 395. C-53/03 Syfait and others of 31 May 2005, ECLI:EU:C:2005:333, I-04609, par. 29. C-503/15 Margarit Panicello of 16 February 2017, ECLI:EU:C:2017:126, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 27. C-274/14 Banco Santander of 21 January 2020, ECLI:EU:C:2020:17, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 51.

²⁸CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Défaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:586, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 48 “(…) the requirement of the independence of the judges pertains to the essential content of the fundamental right to a fair trial, which is of cardinal importance as a guarantee of the protection of all the rights

It is inappropriate to remain with an interpretation of Art. 47 CFREU (Picod, Van Droogbenbroeck, 2020) which corresponds to Art. 6 ECHR, as well as the rich jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) (Picod, 2021) for the protection of equivalent protection and offered by the ECHR and also managed by Art. 52, par. 3 (Bobek, Adams Prassl, 2020; Jarass, 2020; Tinière, Vial, 2020; Peers and others, 2021; Ripol Carulla, Ligartemendia Uceizabarrena, 2022; Casarosa, Moraru, 2022)

The *Juizes Portugueses* case has led us to understand that Art. 19, par. 1 has a close connection with Art. 2 TEU given that it allows to oppose the related or systemic threats (Lenaerts, 2019)²⁹, as well as the independence of the judges of the Member States by undermining the principle of respect for the rule of law. In the face of any kind of threat, the connection with the supreme principles of Art. 2 TEU makes it possible to overcome the principle of procedural autonomy of the Member States (Van Rossem, 2013; Klamert, 2017; Contartese, 2018;

deriving from the individual by Union law and of the safeguard of values common to the Member States set out in Article 2 TEU, in particular, of the value of the rule of law (...)" C-297/17, C-318/17, C-319/17, C-438/17, Ibrahim and others of 19 March 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:219, published in the electronic Reports of the cases.

²⁹See the conclusions of the Advocate General Tanchev in cases: C-558/18 and C-563/18, *Miasto Łowicz e Prokurator Generalny zastępowany przez Prokuraturę Krajową* of 24 September 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:775, par. 125, affirmed that: "(...) Article 19, paragraph 1, second subparagraph, TU is limited to structural violations that compromise the very essence of the independence of the judges (...)".

Östlund, 2019). The reference to Art. 19, par. 1 lets go the scope of Art. 47 CFREU, where due to the final provisions it finds application limited to the observance of Art. 19, par. 1. The CJEU (Bobek, Adams Prassl, 2020; Ripol Carulla, Ligartemendia Uceizabarrena, 2022) has clarified that the scope *ratione materiae* of Art. 19 TEU states that:

“(...) this provision concerns the areas covered by Union law, irrespective of the situation in which Member States implement this law, in accordance with article 51(1) of the CFREU (...)”³⁰.

The continuing jurisprudence has developed in the cases of Poland various criteria of independence as well as the potential systemic default of the rule of law under articles 2 and 19, para. 1 TEU (Schwarze, Becker, Hatje, Schoo, 2019; Matthes, 2022). Art. 2 TEU was based on the order of the CJEU of 15 November 2018³¹ where it was stated that:

“(...) the requirement of the independence of judges pertains to the essential content of the fundamental right to a fair trial, which is of cardinal importance as a guarantee of the protection of all the rights deriving from Union law to the individual and of the safeguarding of the values common to the Member States set out in Article 2 TEU, in particular, of the value of the rule of law (...)” (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019; Matthes, 2022).

The related question of the independence of national judges as a protagonist element of the principle of the rule of law was only examined by the Court from the point of view of article 19 TEU in the *Miasto Łowicz* of September 2019 judgment alone.

³⁰CJEU, C-64/16 *Associação Sindical dos Juizes Portugueses* of 27 February 2018, op. cit., par. 29.

³¹Order of the President of the Court in case: C-619/18 *Commission v. Poland* of 15 November 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:910, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 21.

In C-619/18 *Commission v. Poland* case (independence of the Supreme Court) (Liakopoulos, 2019c; Bakò, 2021)³², the CJEU reconfirmed the principles already developed in the *Wightman*, *Juízes Portugueses* and *Achmea* judgments concluding that:

“(...) article 19 TEU, which concretizes the value of the rule of law affirmed in article 2 TEU entrusts national courts and the CJEU with the task of ensuring the full application of EU law in all Member States as well as the judicial protection available to individuals under EU law (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019). The independence of the judicial bodies, intrinsically linked to the task of judging, constitutes an essential aspect of the fundamental right to a fair trial, which is of cardinal importance as a guarantee of the protection of all rights deriving from the individual from Union law and the safeguarding of the values common to the Member States set out in article 2 TEU, in particular the value of the rule of law (...)”³³.

The same thesis was also followed in the *Commission v. Poland* case of 5 November 2019 (independence of ordinary courts) (Daminova, 2019; Scheppele, Vladimirovich Kochenov, Grabowska-Moroz, 2020; Liakopoulos, 2022)³⁴ and the *A.K.* case of 19 November 2019 (Birkinshaw, 2020)³⁵. The latter judgment summarized the various and different aspects of

32CJEU, C-619/18, *Commission v. Poland* of 24 June 2019, op. cit., Press release n. 159/18, Luxembourg, 19 October 2018. Order of the vice President of the court in case C-619/18 R, *European Commission v. Poland*.

33CJEU, C-619/18, *Commission v. Poland* of 24 June 2019, op. cit., par. 58.

34CJEU, C-192/18, *Commission v. Poland* (Indépendance des juridictions de droit commun) of 5 November 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:924, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 98 and 106. According to Liakopoulos: “(...) although it was not referred to the cited jurisprudence according to my opinion the jurisprudence used by the CJEU conflicts with the effective protection of the adversarial principle and especially with the principle of the fair trial, according to Art. 6, par. 3 TEU and Art. 47 of the CFREU and the best interest of the administration of justice (...)”.

35CJEU, C-585/18, *A.K.* (Indépendance de la chambre disciplinaire de la Cour suprême) of 19 November 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:982, published in the electronic Reports of the cases.

judicial independence based on the relevant articles 2 and 19, para. 1, TEU, as well as the differentiation between internal and external dimension that the CJEU has developed in the *Juízes Portugueses* and *LM* cases³⁶. The CJEU stated that:

“(...) the independence requirement has two aspects. The first aspect, of an external nature, presupposes that the body concerned exercises its functions in full autonomy, without being subject to any hierarchical or of subordination towards anyone and without receiving orders or instructions from any source, with the consequence of being therefore protected from external interventions or pressures capable of compromising the independence of judgment of its members and of influencing their decisions (...). The second aspect, of an internal nature, is linked to the notion of impartiality and concerns the equidistance from the parties to the dispute and their respective interests regarding the object of the latter. This aspect requires respect for objectivity and the absence of any interest in the resolution of the dispute other than the strict application of the legal norm (...)”³⁷.

With regard to the guarantees of independence and respect for the legislative, executive and impartiality powers, the CJEU stated that:

“(...) the existence of rules, relating in particular to the composition of the body, the appointment, the duration of the functions as well as the causes of abstention, recusal and revocation of its members, make it possible to dispel any legitimate doubt that individuals may have regarding the impermeability of this body with respect to external elements and its neutrality with respect to opposing interests (...)”³⁸.

Finally, with the *A.K.* case and the reference to Art. 19 TEU the value of the rule of law is sanctioned by Art. 2 TEU, entrusting national judges and the CJEU with the relative responsibility of

³⁶CJEU, C-585/18, *A.K* (Indépendance de la chambre disciplinaire de la Cour suprême) of 19 November 2019, op. cit., parr. 63-65.

³⁷CJEU, C-585/18, *A.K* (Indépendance de la chambre disciplinaire de la Cour suprême) of 19 November 2019, op. cit., parr. 121-122.

³⁸CJEU, C-585/18, *A.K* (Indépendance de la chambre disciplinaire de la Cour suprême) of 19 November 2019, op. cit., parr. 123-124.

guaranteeing the full application of the law of the Union to all Member States, as well as the relative jurisdiction deriving from this law³⁹.

With the C-791/19R, *Commission v. Poland* of 8 April 2020 case the CJEU highlighted the connection between the independence of judges and the rule of law as well as the related provisional measures according to Art. 279 TFEU regarding the Polish law on the disciplinary chamber of magistrates (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019). According to the CJEU the principle of separation of powers which characterizes the functioning of the rule of law and the independence of judges from the legislative and executive powers must be guaranteed. In this regard, judges need to be protected from external intervention or pressure that could jeopardize their independence⁴⁰.

What happens with the connection between Art. 2 TEU and Art. 19, par. 1 TEU? Also in this case according to the CJEU Art. 19, par. 1 TEU is materialized and is fully anchored with article 2 according to the supreme values allowed for the conferment of Art. 19, par. 1, with a concrete character and with the relative depth that finds its basis for the first time in the *Juízes Portugueses* judgment. A connection that is now concrete, full,

³⁹CJEU, C-585/18, *A.K (Indépendance de la chambre disciplinaire de la Cour suprême)* of 19 November 2019, op. cit., par. 167.

⁴⁰CJEU, C-192/18, *Commission v. Poland* of 5 November 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:924, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, parr. 98 and 106.

precise and above all reciprocal.

Area of freedom, security and justice: mutual trust according to the values of Art. 2 TEU

Recalling *ex novo* the *Juizes Portugueses* case where it was stated that mutual trust between Member States is based on the fundamental premise that Member States share a set of common values on which the Union is founded, i.e. the values of Article 2 TEU, including respect for the rule of law⁴¹. Articles 2 and 19 TEU have been used several times in the framework of the European arrest warrant, which is based on the principle of mutual trust. (Van Raepenbusch, 2016; Lenaerts, 2017; Jacque, 2018; Storskrubb, 2018; Marzo, 2018; Rizcallah, 2019; Lenaerts, 2019; Bribosia, Joncheray, Navasartian, 2019). What interests us is the relationship of the European arrest warrant with the authority of a Member State that does not respect the values of Art. 2 TEU and refuses delivery to the competent authorities. The CJEU relied on the one hand on the content in *speciem* Art. 1, par. 3 of the Decision 2002/584 which actually took into consideration the Articles 2 and 6 TEU, recital 10 where it was stated that:

“(...) the European arrest warrant mechanism is based on a high degree of trust between Member States. The implementation of this mechanism can only be suspended in the event of a serious and persistent breach by a Member State of the principles enshrined in article 6, par. 1 of the Treaty on European Union, as established by the Council in application of article 7, par.

⁴¹CJEU, C-192/18, *Commission v. Poland* of 5 November 2019, *op. cit.*, par. 30.

1, of the same treaty, and with the consequences provided for in paragraph 2 of the same article (...)" (Liakopoulos, 2019b).

The CJEU examined the issue *ex novo* in the LM judgment⁴².

The Luxembourg judges took into consideration that the law of the Union is based on the values of Art. 2 TEU⁴³, as well as the argument of the independence of the judges which:

"(...) is of cardinal importance as a guarantee of the protection of all the rights deriving from the individual's Union law and of the safeguarding of the values common to the Member States set out in article 2 TEU, in particular the value of the rule of law (...)"⁴⁴,

as it has been inserted in article 19 TEU⁴⁵. Thus, according to the CJEU⁴⁶ the principle of mutual recognition recognized and referred to in the last case cited:

"(...) represents the "cornerstone" of judicial cooperation in criminal matters; therefore, if the execution of the European arrest warrant is the rule, the refusal to execute it is an exception, which must be interpreted restrictively (...)"⁴⁷.

An affirmation that has already been inspired in jurisprudence by the Aranyosi and Căldăraru cases:

42CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Dèfaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, op. cit.

43CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Dèfaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, op. cit., par. 35.

44CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Dèfaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, op. cit., par. 48.

45CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Dèfaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, op. cit. parr. 50-51.

46CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Dèfaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, op. cit. parr. 41-44.

47CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Dèfaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, op. cit. parr. 41-44.

“(…) the principles of mutual recognition and trust between Member States can be made “in exceptional circumstances”, when the surrender procedure risks to induce inhuman or degrading treatment, within the meaning of section 4 of the CFREU, of the requested person (…)”(Mansell, 2011; Smith, 2013; Tinsley, 2013; Foster, 2014; Sybesma-Knol, 2015; Swoboda, 2015; Bachmaier, 2015; Vervaele, 2015; Gàspàr-Szilàgy, 2016; Vovend’eerdt, 2016; Guiresse, 2016; Niblock, 2016; Broberg, 2016; Woods, Watson, 2017)⁴⁸.

With regard to the derogation from this rule in the event that the

⁴⁸CJEU, joined cases C-404/15 and C-659/15, P. Aranyosi and R. Căldăraru of 5 April 2016, ECLI:EU:C:2016:198, published in the electronic Reports of the cases. The CJEU has gone further on the mutual recognition and has been based on another interpretative way stating that the Art. 3 of the ECHR and 4 of the CFREU must be interpreted: “(…) in a convergence between (…)“. In particular the Advocate General Yves Bot which is affirmed that: “(…) In the AG’s search for balance he considers first whether Article 1(3) FDEAW constitutes a ground for non-execution of an arrest warrant. He rejects such a notion for the following three reasons. First off, interpreting Article 1(3) as a non-execution ground would run counter to the phrasing of that Article, which due to its place and wording does not express a non-execution ground, but rather the principle of mutual trust. Secondly, such a notion would not be in agreement with the EU legislator’s intent to create a system of surrender with exhaustively enumerated non-recognition grounds, whereby, in addition to the grounds in Articles 3, 4, and 4a FDEAW, only in the exceptional circumstances described in Recitals (10) and (13) surrender can be suspended or removal, expulsion or extradition can be prohibited. Last, a ground of non-recognition in Article 1(3) would severely damage mutual trust between judicial authorities on which the Framework Decision is based and would, as a result, make the principle of mutual recognition meaningless (… talking about another principle-value of the Union, that of proportionality as a balancing of interests and the widening of the discretionary sphere of the internal judge, and the circumstances in speciem. Criminal cooperation does not seem to be comparable with the similar ground and dates back to the experience of the single market, in terms of decisive jurisprudential protagonism. Let us not forget that criminal cooperation has been based on the definition of common minimum standards for delineating spaces and limits of cooperation between judicial and police authorities in the areas selected by the Member States and by the Union legislator. Of course we can speak of a positive and normative unification for years in the criminal sector and especially after the Treaty of Lisbon the merit belongs to the principle of mutual recognition of judicial decisions which continues to guarantee a median solution to integration that is summarized in the protection of rights fundamental rights, the inalienable rights of individuals and a continuous progress dictated by the Member States towards an increasingly active and proactive contribution, a harbinger of innovations and achievements with the main objective among others the continuous accelerated integration but within a harmonious development and development of all the individual interest and not the state one (…)”.

non-compliance with the values of Art. 2 TEU is assessed and in practice is noted by the issuing state, the CJEU repeats in the LM case and clarifies the impact on the execution of the European arrest warrant for various procedures that are involved and included in Art. 7 TEU⁴⁹. Indeed the CJEU stated that:

“(...) the issuing Member State has been the subject of a reasoned proposal by the Commission, adopted under Article 7, par. 1 TEU, for the Council to establish that there is a risk evidence of a serious breach by that Member State of the values referred to in article 2 TEU, such as in particular that of the rule of law, due to attacks on the independence of national courts, and the executing judicial authority has elements capable of demonstrating the existence of systemic deficiencies at the level of the judiciary of that state. A concrete assessment on a case-by-case basis is necessary (...) only in exceptional circumstances in which said authority ascertains, as a result, a concrete and precise assessment of the case in point, that there are serious and proven reasons to believe that the person subject to that European arrest warrant runs, following his surrender to the issuing judicial authority, a real risk of infringement of his fundamental right to an independent judge and, therefore, of the essential content of his fundamental right to a fair trial (...)”⁵⁰.

For the confirmation of the exceptional nature of the refusal and the execution of the arrest warrant, the CJEU stated that “it added a number of elements that the national judge must examine”⁵¹.

49CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Dèfaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, op. cit., parr. 69-71.

50CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Dèfaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, op. cit., par. 73.

51CJEU, C-216/18 PPU 2018 LM Minister for Justice and Equality (Dèfaillances du système judiciaire) of 25 July 2018, op. cit., parr. 72-76: “In the context of such an assessment, the executing judicial authority must, in particular, examine to what extent the systemic or generalized deficiencies concerning the independence of the judges of the issuing Member State, attested by the elements at its disposal, are suitable for have an impact at the level of the courts of that Member State competent to know the proceedings to which the requested person will be subjected. If from this examination it appears that these deficiencies are likely to affect these judges, the executing judicial authority has yet to assess, in the light of the specific concerns expressed by the person concerned and the information that may be provided by the

In the case instead that the issuing state is part of a decision of the European Council and according to the conditions of Art. 7, par. 2 TEU is thus ascertained the serious and persistent violation in the issuing Member State of the principles of article 2 TEU such as those which are inherent to the rule of law. Thus following the suspension by the Council of the application of the framework Decision 2002/584 before the state, the executing judicial authority can automatically refuse the execution of any arrest warrant issued by the relevant authorities of that state without the need to carry out a precise assessment of the real risk that the person concerned runs (Wallace, Pollack, Young, 2010; Edward, Lane, 2013; D'Alessio, Kronenberger, Placco, 2013, Varju, 2014; Limbach, 2015; Frenz, 2015; Daniel Sokol, Lianos, 2016; Ravasi, 2017; Tomljenović, Bobiroga-Vukobrat, Butorac Malnar, Kunda, 2017; Castillo de la torre, Gippini Fournier, 2017; Veenbrink, 2019; Varju, 2019; Sousa Ferro, 2019; Lenaerts, 2019)⁵².

latter, if serious reasons exist and proven to believe that that person runs a real risk of violation of his fundamental right to an independent judge and, therefore, of the essential content of his fundamental right to a fair trial, taking into account his personal situation and the nature of the crime for which it is pursued and the factual circumstances underlying the European arrest warrant. In addition, the executing judicial authority must request the issuing judicial authority, pursuant to Article 15 (2) of Framework Decision 2002/584, any additional information it deems necessary for the assessment of the existence of such a risk (...)"

52CJEU, joined cases C-238, 244 and 245, 247, 250 to 252, 254/99 P, Limburgse Vinyl Maatschappij and others v. Commission of 15 February 2002, ECLI:EU:C:2002:582, I-08375. C-135/07 P and C-137/07, Erste Group Bank and others v. Commission of 24 September 2009, ECLI:EU:C:2009:576, I-0868. GC, T-446/05, Amann & Söhne and others v. Commission of 28 April 2010,

The violation as well as the risk of a violation of the values envisaged by Art. 2 TEU has, according to recital 10 of the framework decision, the corresponding consequences as regards the possibility for the enforcement judge to refuse exceptionally and after an evaluation and in a general way the execution of the arrest warrant. The link between Articles 2 and 7 TEU remain important and an anchor of the conditions for non-execution of the European arrest warrant relying on a specific provision without limit and outside the proper scope of Article 2 TEU. This jurisprudence is limited to the European arrest warrant and does not continue with any other general rule which imposes the violation of Art. 2 TEU thus invoking only the Institutions of the Union that have initiated one of the procedures provided for by Art. 7 TEU (Schwarze, Becker, Hatje, Schoo, 2019).

After the LM case mutual trust and respect for the fundamental values of Art. 2 TEU have been reiterated in various cases involving the European Arrest Warrant, as a respect and necessary element to maintain mutual trust which is the basis of mutual recognition (Fitzmaurice, Merkouris, 2020; Morano-

ECLI:EU:T:2010:165, II-01255. T-138/07, Shindler Holding and others v. Commission of 13 July 2011, ECLI:EU:T:2011:362, II-04819. T-587/08, Fresh del Monte Produce v. Commission of 14 March 2013, ECLI:EU:T-2013:129, published in the electronic Reports of the cases. T-400/09, Eeka Granulate and non ferrum Metallpulver v. Commission of 12 December 2012, ECLI:EU:T:2012:675, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, parr. 23-27.

Foadi, Andreadakis, 2020; Scholten, Brenninkmeijer, 2020)⁵³.

Principles, notions, affirmations, rights that move within a circle called an area of freedom, security and justice based on the principle of mutual trust of the Member States such as asylum and international protection. Within this spirit also the CJEU in the Jawo case requests that each of the Member States:

“(…) considers, except in exceptional circumstances, that all the other Member States respect Union law and, in particular, fundamental rights and common values on which the Union is founded, as set out in article 2 TEU, and that their respective national legal systems are capable of providing equivalent and effective protection of the fundamental rights recognized by the CFREU (…)” (Jan Kuijper, Amtenbrink, Curtin, De Witte, McDonnell, 2018)⁵⁴.

Protection of fundamental rights and Art. 2 TEU

Articles 6 and 2 TEU are “miraculous” given that they include in their existence many rights as stated in the founding values that promote the rank of these rights and essential values for the legal order of the Union (Di Federico, 2010; Ghazaryan, 2014; Rossi, 2015; Rossi, 2017; Fartunova.Michel, Marzo, 2018). First of all we can say that Art. 6 and the CFREU together with Art. 19, par. 1 TEU are the preamble, “the light area” of Art. 2 TEU

53CJEU, C-327/18 R O of 19 September 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:733, published in the electronic Reports of the cases. C-551/18 PPU, I.K (exécution d'une peine complémentaire) of 6 December 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:991, published in the electronic Reports of the cases. C-128/18 Dumitru-Tudor Dorobantu of 15 October 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:857, not yet published, parr. 45-46. C-631/17 Inspecteur van de Belastingdienst of 8 May 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:381, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, parr. 35-36.

54CJEU, C-163/17 Abubacarr Jawo v. Bundesrepublik Deutschland of 19 March 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:218, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 80-81.

(Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). A violation of fundamental rights with the involvement of all these articles is the application not only of Articles 2 and 6 TEU and as a consequence of the CFREU but also an umbrella which includes below the relevant limitations in its final provisions which also takes into consideration Art. 51 CFREU (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). Let us not forget that already the Advocate General Tanchev, in his conclusions in the *Commission v. Poland* case (independence of the ordinary courts)⁵⁵, stated that:

“(...) the limitations inherent in the CFREU, from which it follows that it applies to Member States only when they implement Union law (article 51, par.1 of the CFREU), cannot be taken to the point of weakening the Commission's duty to protect the fundamental values of the Union contained in article 2 TEU, constituting them part of the common European constitutional heritage (...) (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019). Flagrant violations or systemic violations of human rights, committed by a Member State outside the scope of EU law, could fall under Article 2 of the TEU (...)” (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019).

The jurisprudence of the CJEU, as can be seen, follows a growing reference to aid in Art. 2 TEU framed as “mandatory” for both the institutions and the Member States and as a consequence for the respect of fundamental rights. The importance of this type of respect goes beyond the need to protect the individual and in the concrete case assume the related implications at a more general and systemic level always in the presence of an inseparable link with the founding values

⁵⁵CJEU, C-192/18, *Commission v. Poland* (Indépendance des juridictions de droit commun) of 5 November 2019, op. cit., par. 72.

of the Union, as an important step in the evolution of the new generation of EU.

Protection of fundamental rights, Art. 2 TEU and principle of democracy

Speaking of democracy in EU law, of course we immediately refer to the general principles and history of European integration. From the jurisprudential point of view, the Puppink case⁵⁶, comes to our mind, which through articles 2 and 10 TEU underlined the mechanism of the citizens' initiative of the Union. Under article 10, par.1 TEU, the functioning of the Union is based on representative democracy, which embodies the value of democracy. The latter constitutes, by virtue of Article 2 TEU, one of the values on which the Union is founded (Liakopoulos, 2019b). In reality it is a “mild” statement that we encounter in the Junqueras case in relation to the protocol on the privileges and immunities of the members of the European Parliament⁵⁷. Why? Because the term of “member of the European Parliament” is not analyzed in the reported protocol given that this is interpreted according to Art. 10, par. 1 TEU, i.e. references to the principle of representative democracy which

⁵⁶CJEU, C-418/18 Patrick Grégor Puppink and others v. Poland of 19 December 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:1113, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 64. See also the conclusions of the Advocate General Bobek in case: C-418/18, Puppink and others v. European Commission of 29 July 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:640, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 67.

⁵⁷CJEU, C-502/19, Oriol Junqueras Vies of 19 December 2019. ECLI:EU:C:2019:1115, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 62-63.

actually embodies the value of democracy according to Art. 2 TEU (Schwarze, Becker, Hatje, Schoo, 2019). It is the same jurisprudence of the CJEU that has told us about the connection of freedom of expression and democracy according to Art. 2 TEU. We recall the *Patriciello* case, where the CJEU clarified:

“(…) that this freedom, as an essential foundation of a democratic and pluralistic society reflecting the values on which the Union is founded, pursuant to article 2 TEU, constitutes a right guaranteed by article 11 of the CFREU (…)” (Broberg, Fenger, 2014)⁵⁸.

In the same spirit we recall the *Tele2Sverige* case, where it was underlined that this freedom is of particular importance in any democratic society. This fundamental right, guaranteed by article 11 of the CFREU, constitutes one of the essential foundations of a democratic and pluralistic society, forming part of the values on which, pursuant to Article 2 TEU, the Union is founded (Greer, Gerards, Slowe, 2018)⁵⁹. Continuing with the *NH Association of Lawyers for LGBTI Rights-Lenford Network*⁶⁰ case where it was stated that freedom of expression is the essential foundation of a democratic and pluralistic society which reflects the values on which the Union is founded, pursuant to article 2 TEU (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019).

Finally, we can speak of an osmosis of fundamental rights in close connection with the founding values of the Union which

⁵⁸CJEU, C-163/10 *Patriciello* of 6 September 2011, ECLI:EU:C:2011:543, I-07565, par. 31.

⁵⁹CJEU, joined cases C-203/15 and C-698/15 *Tele2 Sverige* of 21 December 2016, ECLI:EU:C:2016:970, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 93.

⁶⁰CJEU, C-507/18 *NH Associazione Avvocatura per i diritti LGBTI-Rete Lenford* of 23 April 2020, ECLI:EU:C:2020:289, not yet published.

can also be manifested in other various sectors such as those of human dignity as we have seen in the K and HF case (Chalmers, Davies, Monti, 2019; Guild, Peers, 2019; Barnard, 2019)⁶¹ or in the freedom of the press (De Miguel Asensio, 2020)⁶².

What are the jurisdictional remedies for the violation of the related values of Art. 2 TEU?

When it comes to judicial remedies and violation of the values of Art. 2 TEU immediately we orient ourselves towards the continuous evolution of the jurisprudence of the CJEU which finds the way to bring us various nuances of interpretation of Art. 2 TEU and related ones.

One point that still remains open for interpretation is the violation of Art. 2 TEU. At the time of the breach the Member State applies the political mechanisms provided for by Art. 7 TEU, i.e. imposition of penalties. But are such mechanisms legal? In a case of a preliminary ruling (Prechhal, Van

⁶¹CJEU, joined cases C-331/16, K. Staatssecretaris van Veiligheid en Justitie and C-366/16, H.F. v. Belgische Staat of 2 May 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:296, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 46: “Furthermore, it is important to stress that the crimes and actions referred to in Article 1, Section F of the Geneva Convention or in Article 12 (2) of Directive 2011/95 constitute a serious threat to fundamental values such as respect of human dignity and human rights, on which, as enshrined in Article 2 TEU, the Union is founded, and to peace, which the Union has as its purpose to promote, in accordance with Article 3 TEU (...)”.

⁶²See also the conclusions of the Advocate General Hogan in case: C-299/17, VG Media Gesellschaft of 13 December 2018, ECLI:EU:C:2018:1004, published in the electronic Reports of the cases, par. 42: “(...) a free and active press is the lifeblood of democracy which, as Article 2 TEU recognizes, is the cornerstone of the Union and its Member States (...)”.

Roermund, Van Roermund, 2008; Andersen, 2012; Terhechte, 2012; Perju, 2018)⁶³ one finds the right of the Union to be contrary to national law and as a consequence all bodies of the Member State showing an interest are required not to apply it. On the other hand, the case of the appeal for non-compliance includes the relative sanction against the Member State in clearly pecuniary terms (Gasso, Sauron, 2021). At this point, a political aspect should be added which ignores the difficulty for the Commission and for the remaining Member States to use the relative procedures which are foreseen by the relative articles such as Art. 258 up to 260 TFEU for the violation of Art. 2 TEU (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019). We can say that this type of difficulty is lower than that which characterizes the initiation of procedures according to Art. 7 TEU (Schwarze, Becker, Hatje, Schoo, 2019). Let us not forget that numerous elements indicate that the mechanisms offered by Art. 7 TEU offers a case of breach of the related values underpinning the Union as an added and extreme protection which is no alternative in relation to ordinary judicial remedies.

The violation of Art. 2 TEU is sanctioned through specific procedures. Some prerequisites for the adoption of such procedures are requested by the Council and the European Council. Although heated political debates occur and many

⁶³CJEU, C-224/01, Köbler v. Republik Österreich of 30 September 2003, ECLI:EU:C:2003:513, I-10239.

times with no way out and as a consequence the non-application of the measures envisaged (Priest, 2016; Bouveresse, Ritleng, 2018)⁶⁴. Art. 2 TEU is not included through an ordinary system of judicial remedies which renders the fundamental values of the Union less protected than any other provision of the treaties. It is not fair to say that the CJEU is granted a power to decide a preliminary ruling procedure (Pertek, 2021) where Art. 2 TEU as an obstacle to a Member State's legislation puts the CJEU to take a position before an infringement action based on the violation of the same article.

The procedures envisaged by Art. 7 TEUs are various and different from each other having as final objective the respect of the related actions. Procedures can lead to the most serious sanction that anyone can imagine, i.e. the suspension of the rights of a Member State while the procedure for non-compliance can open the relative suspension of the rights of a Member State according to the articles provided for by the Treaties.

The non-compliance procedure can open the way to a conviction

⁶⁴The procedure referred to in Article 7 (1) of the TEU has been launched against Hungary. Although it will not be easy for the Council to find a 4/5 majority to impose the surveillance procedure, on 24 March 2020 the European Parliament, underlining the binding nature of Article 2 TEU and also referring to the CFREU, announced the use of the preventive mechanism. On 11 May 2020, the Vice-President of the European Commission Vera Jourová therefore announced: “(...) that she will address the European Parliament in relation to the extraordinary measures taken in Hungary during the COVID crisis¹⁹. She said she was “worried” about the situation in Hungary. This does not clarify, however, whether the Commission will launch infringement proceedings against Hungary to establish a violation of Article 2 TEU (...)”.

and to possible fines in accordance with Art. 260 TFEU (Berry, Homewood, Bogusz, 2019; Schwarze, Becker, Hatje, Schoo, 2019; Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). The ordinary jurisdictional remedies are bearers of a balancing consensus of the principle of proportionality but also more punctual and adherent to the factual circumstances that respect the general political evaluations, i.e. the basis of the procedures provided for by Art. 7 TEU. Striking things through jurisprudence lose their deterrent effect which does not remain to resort to conventional ways. Therefore, political and jurisdictional remedies are independent of each other (Hillion, 2016a; Hillionb). When the legislator tries to create a link between the violation of the values of Art. 2 TEU and the procedures of Art. 7 TEU, as we have seen in the case of the European arrest warrant, political and jurisdictional choices go hand in hand and create synergies of hierarchical rank. *Ubi lex voluit, ubi noluit tacuit* is a motto of the CJEU that allows us to clearly state that the violation of values according to Art. 2 TEU are not facilitated according to Art. 7, par. 1 TEU and vice versa. Because there is no one-to-one correspondence between Art. 2 and 7 TEUs (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021). The condition of Art. 2 TEU is the result and the beginning of Art. 7 TEU but not necessarily a necessary condition and application of Art. 2 TEU (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019).

And the rising question is whether Art. 2 TEU can be invoked and be combined with another provision of the law of the EU? Is this provision at the same time the embodiment of the first or also a situation in itself?

Art. 2 TEU lends a large number of links to other articles of the treaty of Lisbon. In the moment of violation of Art. 2 TEU as well as of other provisions of the law of the Union, an action for non-performance, as well as a request for a preliminary reference will have as its object the common violation of the provisions of Art. 2 TEU (Kellerbauer, Klamert, Tomkin, 2019; Pertek, 2021; Spieker, 2021). By adding to Art. 2 TEU the ability to work as “a strengthener of the reasoning of the relevant judgment” we underline the relative seriousness and systemic aspects of the breach. Therefore, the actions for non-fulfillment or for preliminary rulings are relative appeals for the violation of Art. 19, par. 1 and 2 TEU, i.e. provisions where one's connection functions as an affirmed materialization of what the judges of the Luxembourg underline with the sentences regarding the articles relating to this analysis⁶⁵.

The rule of law and also other rights etc. can be linked to Articles 2 and 19 TEU (Elòsegui, Miron, Motoc, 2021). The protection of the rights included in Art. 6 TEU and in CFREU

⁶⁵The European Commission has recently filed an appeal for failure to fulfill obligations in Poland, based on Article 19 (1) TEU (CJEU, C-791/19, Commission v. Poland of 8 April 2020, ECLI:EU:C:2020:277, not yet published).

have a close connection with Art. 2 TEU. We understand that within the scope of the CFREU the remedies for the joint violation of one or more provisions are combined with Art. 2 TEU. This occurs for serious and systemic violations of freedom of the press and freedom of association but also for other rights provided for in various articles of the CFREU.

There is also a second hypothesis where the European Commission or a Member State can start the relative infringement procedure even in the moment of absence of the relative provisions of the law of the EU using only Art. 2 TEU. In this case the situation is complicated given that the initiation of an action for non-performance is based exclusively and only on Art. 2 TEU (Kochenov, 2015; Smith, 2015; Chalmers, 2015; Schmidt, 2018; De Naclares, 2019; Spieker, 2019; Bård, Śledzińska Simon, 2019; Platon, 2019), perhaps also on the use of the preliminary ruling procedure (Drinòczy, 2010; Von Bogdandy, 2012; Lenaerts, 2013; Tatham, 2013; Dawson, 2013; Adams, De Waele, Meeusen, Straetmans, 2013; Kochenov, 2013; Kochenov, 2014; Kochenov, 2015; Kochenov, Pech, 2015; Gerken, 2015-2016; Polzin, 2016; Faraguna, 2016; Ninet, Gardner, 2016; Delledonne, 2016; Silveira, Mckenny Engstöm, 2016; Jakab, Kochenov, 2017; Bobek, 2017; Perju, 2018; Albert, Emrahoder, 2018; Drinòczy, 2018; Giegerich, 2019; Hiilpert, 2019; Fabbrini, Sajò, 2019; Balkin, 2019; Kucherenko,

Klochko, 2019; Perju, 2020; Gasso, Sauron, 2021)⁶⁶. The doubts are varied above all for the precise and “pure” nature of Art. 2 TEU which provides for an intermediate solution that goes as far as the appeal of the infringement procedure, the violation of Art. 2 TEU and the principle of loyal cooperation (Art. 4, par. 3 TEU), i.e. a principle that reinforces the obligation to comply with the relative provisions of the treaties (Closa, Kochenov, Weiler, 2014). The appeal for infringement and for violation of Art. 2 TEU is an entry obstacle for the new states (Art. 49 TEU) since in reality requires the maintenance of minimum standards not only during the negotiations but also after accession (Liakopoulos, 2018b).

Within this context, the CJEU as a promoter of solutions and integrative evolution of the EU law responds to a question of reference for a preliminary ruling that Art. 2 TEU alone and in combination with another article stands as an obstacle to a national legislation that can justify the infringement procedure in relation to the violation of Art. 2 TEU (Spieker, 2021). This

⁶⁶According to Lenaerts: “(...) an essential component of the national identity of Member States, the democratic arrangements provided for by national constitutions are not to be undermined by EU law (...) for national constitutional courts, the EU’s commitment to respecting national democracies is an essential element without which European integration would come to an immediate halt (...)”. According to Ninet, Gardner: “(...) In the United States, distinct cultural, linguistic, and religious groups tend to be geographically dispersed, and even where they are concentrated, as in urban areas, they tend not to comprise majorities capable of exercising political control at the regional level. That dispersion, combined with a longstanding national project of assimilation, has tended to undermine the conditions necessary for ethnocultural distinctiveness to evolve into the kind of substate nationalism sometimes encountered elsewhere. As a result, American states today rarely assert any kind of distinct identity or sovereignty (...)”.

hypothesis concerns the systemic gaps of the rule of law or the massive and violent limitations of the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens who do not fall within the circle of application of the CFREU and cannot be sanctioned on the basis of the latter. Of course we are talking about situations in extremis and in the presence of which the recourse to extreme measures would only have the objective of preserving the founding values of the Union which constitutes the pillars that find the basis on a founding social contract in the EU. It is surprising if the Institutions of the Union or other Member States use all the legal means and judicial remedies that they have in their own hands and from the Treaties themselves. We will find in this problem a decisive answer perhaps from the CJEU in the future.

References

- Abazi, V. (2019). *Official secrets and oversight in the EU: Law and practice of classified information*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 999ss.
- Andersen, S. (2012). *The enforcement of EU law: The role of the European Commission*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, pp. 62-67.
- Antal, A. (2019). *The rise of Hungarian populism: State autocracy and the Orbán regime*. Emerland Group Publishing, London.
- Arigho, R. (2014). The supremacy of EU law: An inevitable revolution or federalism in action?. *Journal of Postgraduate Research*, 10ss.
- Ashiagbor, D., Countouris, N., Lianos, I. (2012). *The European Union after the Treaty of Lisbon*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 109-135.
- Bachmaier, L. (2015). Mutual recognition instruments and the role of the CJEU: The grounds for non-execution. *New Journal of European Criminal Law*, 5 (4), 505ss.
- Bakò, B.C. (2021). Hungary's latest experiences with Article 2 TEU: The need for "informed" EU sanctions. In A. Von Bogdandy, P. Bogdanowicz, I. Canor, C. Grabenwarter, M. Taborowski, M. Schmidt (eds). *Defending checks and balances in EU Member States*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 39ss.

- Baray, A. (2017). *Judicial enforcement and implementation of EU law*. Bruylant, Bruxelles.
- Bård, P., Śledzińska Simon, A. (2019). Rule of law infringement procedures. A proposal to extend the EU's rule of law toolbox. *CEPS*, 9.
- Barents, R. (2016). *Remedies and procedures before the EC courts*. Kluwer Law International, New York.
- Barents, R. (2020). *Remedies and procedures before the EU courts*. Kluwer Law International New York.
- Barnard, C. (2019). *The substantive law of the European Union*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 484ss.
- Barnard, C., Peers, (2017). *European Union law*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 788ss.
- Bernier, A. (2012). Constructing and legitimating: Transnational jurist networks and the making of a constitutional practice of European law. *Contemporary European History*, 21, 400ss.
- Berry, E., Homewood, M.J., Bogusz, B. (2019). *Complete EU law: Text, cases and materials*. Oxford University Press, Oxford
- Billing, F.M.W. (2016). *The right to silence in transnational criminal proceedings. Comparative law perspectives*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 323ss.
- Biondi, A., Birkinshaw, P.J., Kendrick, M. (2018). *Brexit: The legal implications*. Kluwer Law International, New York.

- Birkinshaw, P.J. (2020). *European public law: The achievement and the brexit challenge*. Kluwer Law International, New York.
- Bitter, S. (2002). Loyalty in the European Union. A review. *German Law Journal*, 3 (3), 4ss.
- Blanke, H.J., Mangiamelli, S. (2021). *Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. A commentary*. ed. Springer, Berlin.
- Blanke, H.J., Villalòn, P.C., Klein, T., Ziller, J. (2015). *Common European legal thinking. Essays in honour of Albrecht Weber*. ed. Springer, Berlin.
- Bobek, M., Adams Prassl, J. (2020). *The EU Charter of fundamental rights in the member states*. Hart Publishing, Oxford & Oregon, Portland.
- Boerger-De Smedt, A. (2012). Negotiating the foundations of EU Law, 1950-1957: The legal history of the Treaties of Paris and Rome. *Contemporary European History*, 21, 339-340.
- Bouveresse, A., Ritleng, D. (2018). *L'effectivité du droit de l'Union européenne*. ed. Larcier, Bruxelles.
- Bovend'eerd, K. (2016). The joined cases Aranyosi and Căldăraru: A new limit to the mutual trust presumption in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice?. *Utrecht Journal of International and European Law*, 32, 112ss.
- Breuer, M. (2019). *Principled resistance to ECtHR judgments. A new paradigm?*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 310ss.

- Bribosia, E., Joncheray, N., Navasartian, A. (2019). *L'Europe au kalèidoscope. Liber amicorum marianne Dony: Etudes européennes*. Editions de l'Université de Bruxelles, Bruxelles.
- Broberg, M., Fenger, N. (2013). *Le renvoi préjudiciel à la Cour de Justice de l'Union Européenne*. ed. Larcier, Bruxelles.
- Broberg, M., Fenger, N. (2014). *Preliminary references to the European Court of Justice*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 350ss.
- Broberg, M.P., Fenger, N. (2016). Preliminary references to the Court of Justice of the European Union and the right to a fair trial under article 6 ECHR. *European Law Review*, 23 (4), 602ss.
- Bruun, N., Lörcher, K., Schömann, I. (2012). *The Lisbon treaty and social Europe*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York.
- Calliess, C., Van Der Schyff, G. (2019) Constitutional identity introduced and its European Union law dimension. In C. Calliess, G. Van Der Schyff. *Constitutional identity in a Europe of multilevel constitutionalism*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 34ss.
- Casarosa, F., Moraru, M. (2022). *The practice of judicial interaction in the field of fundamental rights. The added value of the Charter of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union*. Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham.

- Casolari, F. (2020). EU loyalty and the protection of Member States' national interests. A mapping of the law. In M. Varju (eds.) *Between compliance and particularism: Member States interests and European Union law*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 49ss.
- Castillo De La Torre, F., Gippini Fournier, E. (2017). *Evidence, proof and judicial review in EU competition law*. Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham, par. 6.162.
- Chalmers, D., Davies, G., Monti, G. (2019). *European Union law*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Churchill, R., Owen, D. (2010). *The EC common fisheries policy*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Cloots, C. (2016). National identity, constitutional identity and sovereignty in the EU. *Netherlands Journal of Legal Philosophy*, 45 (2), 84ss.
- Contartese, C. (2018). The autonomy of the EU legal order in the ECJ's external relations case law: From the "essential" to the "specific characteristics" of the Union and back again. *Common Market Law Review*, 54, 1628ss.
- Contiades, X., Fotiadou, A. (2016). *Participatory constitutional change: The people as amenders of the constitution*. Taylor & Francis, New York, 201ss.
- Conway, G. (2015). *European Union law*. ed. Routledge, London & New York.

- Corthaut, T. (2012). *EU ordre public*. Kluwer Law International, New York.
- Coutts, S. (2019). *Citizenship, crime and community in the European Union*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York.
- Craig, P., De Búrca, G. (2011). *The evolution of EU law*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Cremona, M. (2020). The opinion procedure under art. 218 (11) TFEU. Reflections in the light of opinion 1/17. *Europe and the World: A Law Review*, 4 (1), 5ss.
- Cremona., M. (2018). *Structural principles in EU external relations law*, Bloomsbury Publishing, New York, 94ss.
- D'Alessio, M.T., Kronenberger, V., Placco, V. (2013). *De Rome à Lisbonne: Les juridictions de l'Union européenne à la croisée des chemins. Mélanges en l'honneur de Paolo Mengozzi*. ed. Bruylant, Bruxelles.
- Daminova, N. (2019). Rule of law vs. Poland and Hungary-an inconsistent approach?. *Hungarian Journal of Legal Studies*, 60 (3), 242ss.
- Daniel Sokol, D., Lianos, I. (2012). *The global limits of competition law*. Stanford University Press, Stanford.
- Davies, G. (2003). *Nationality discrimination in the european internal market*. Kluwer Law International, New York, 203ss.
- Davies, G., Auelj, M. (2018). *Research handbook on legal pluralism and European Union law*. Edward Elgar Publishers,

Cheltenham, 400ss.

De Baere, G., Roes, T. (2015). EU loyalty as good faith. *International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, 64 (4), 834ss.

De Baere, G., Wouters, J. (2016). *The contribution of international and supranational courts to the rule of law*. Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham.

De Miguel Asensio, P. (2020). *Conflict of laws and the internet*. Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham.

De Nanclares, J.M.P. (2019). La Unión europea como comunidad de valores: A vueltas con la crisis de la democracia y del estado de derecho. *Teoría y Realidad Constitucional*, 43.

De Witte, B. (2014). Article 53. In S. Peers et al. (eds). *The EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, A Commentary*. Hart Publishing, Oxford & Oregon, Portland, 1523-1538.

Decheva, M. (2018). *Recht der europäischen Union*. ed. Nomos, Baden-Baden.

Di Federico, G. (2010). *The EU Charter of fundamental rights: From declaration to binding instrument*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 75ss.

Di Federico, G. (2019). The potential of article 4(2) TEU in the solution of constitutional clashes based on alleged violations of national identity and the quest for adequate (judicial) standards. *European Public Law*, 25, 347ss.

Dobbs, M. (2015). The shifting battleground of article 4 (2)

TEU. Evolving national identities and the corresponding need for EU management?. *European Journal of Current Legal Issues*, 21 (2).

Dorssemont, F., Lörcher, K., Clauwaer, S. (2019). *The Charter of fundamental rights of the EU and the employment relation*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York.

Duque, E.E. (2013). National identity as flexibility clause. Granting member states a margin of appreciation. *Lund Student EU Law Review*, 2, 38ss.

Eckes, C. (2020). Disciplining Member States: EU loyalty in external relations. *Cambridge Yearbook of European Legal Studies*, 22, 90ss.

Eckes, C. (2020). The autonomy of the EU legal order. *Europe and the World: A Law Review*, 4 (1), 6ss.

Edward, D.A.O., Lane, R. (2013). *Edward and Lane on European Union law*. Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham.

Egan, M. (2013). Toward a new history in european law: The wine in old bottles?. *American University of International Law Review*, 28 (5), 1226ss.

Elòsegui, M., Miron, A., Motoc, I. (2021). *The rule of law in Europe. Recent challenges and judicial responses*. ed. Springer, Berlin.

Faraguna, P. (2017). Constitutional identity in the EU-a shield or a sword?. *German Law Journal*, 18, 1636ss.

- Fartunova-Michel, M., Marzo, C. (2018). *Les dimensions de la reconnaissance mutuelle en droit de l'Union européenne*. ed. Bruylant, Bruxelles.
- Fichera, M. (2018). *The foundations of the EU as a polity*. Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham.
- Fitzmaurice, M., Merkouris, P. (2020). *Treaties in motion. The evolution of treaties from formation to termination*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Folsom, T.H. (2017). *Principles of European Union law, including Brexit*. West Academic, Minnesota, 278ss.
- Foster, N. (2014). *European Union law directions*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 51ss.
- Frenz, W. (2015). *Handbook of EU competition law*. ed. Springer, Berlin.
- Frischhut, M. (2022). *The ethical spirit of EU values. Status quo of the Union of values and future direction of travel*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 182-184.
- Gàspàr-Szilágy, S. (2016). Joined cases Aranyosi and Căldăraru. Converging human rights standards, mutual trust and new grounds for postponing a European arrest warrant. *European Journal of Crime, Criminal Law and Criminal Justice*, 24 (1), 198ss.
- Gasso, A., Sauron, J.L. (2021). *Droit processuel européen*. Legitech, Luxembourg.

Ghazaryan, N. (2014). *The european neighbour policy and the democratic values of the EU: A legal analysis*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York, 16ss.

Grabenwarter, C., Pabel, K. (2021). *Europäische Menschenrechts Konvention*. C.H. Beck, Helbing Lichtenhahn Verlag, Basel, Manz, Wien.

Granat, M., Granat, K. (2019). *The constitution of Poland. A contextual analysis*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York.

Greer, S., Gerards, J., Slove, R. (2018). *Human rights in the Council of Europe and the European Union: Achievements trends and challenges*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge

Guasteferro, B. (2012). Beyond the exceptionalism of constitutional conflicts: The ordinary functions of the identity clause. *Yearbook of European Law*, 31, 268ss.

Guild, E., Peers, S. (2019). *Citizenship directive: A commentary*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Guinchard, E., Granger, M.P. (2016). *The new EU judiciary. An analysis of current judicial reforms*. Kluwer Law International, New York.

Guirese, M. (2016, avril, 12). Confiance mutuelle et mandat d'arrêt européen: Evolution ou inflexion de la Cour de justice?.

GDR-ELSJ: <http://www.gdr-elsj.eu/2016/04/12/cooperation-judiciaire-penale/confiance-mutuelle-et-mandat-darret-europeen-evolution-ou-inflexion-de-la-cour-de-justice/>

Halbestram, D. (2015) It's autonomy stupid. A modest defense of Opinion 2/13 on EU accession to the ECHR, and a way forward. *Michigan Law Paper* 105.

Halleslov Storgaard, L. (2015). European Union law autonomy versus European fundamental rights protection. On opinion 2/13 on EU accession to the ECHR. *Human Rights Law Review*, 15 (3), 487ss.

Halmai, G. (2018). Abuse of constitutional identity: The Hungarian Constitutional Court on interpretation of article E) (2) of the fundamental law. *Review of Central & East European Law*, 43 (1), 24ss.

Haratsch, A., Koenig, C., Pechstein, M. (2020). *Europarecht*. Mohr Siebeck, Tübingen.

Hatje, A., Terhechte, J.P., Müller-Graff, P.C. (2018). *Europarechtswissenschaft*. ed. Nomos, Baden-Baden.

Hillion, C. (2016a). Overseeing the rule of law in the European Union Legal mandate and means, SIEPS. European Policy Analysis, 1:

https://www.sieps.se/en/publications/2016/overseeing-the-rule-of-law-in-the-european-union-legal-mandate-and-means-20161epa/Sieps_2016_1_epa

Hillion, C. (2016b). Overseeing the rule of law in the EU: Legal mandate and means. In C. Closa, D. Kochenov (eds.). *Reinforcing rule of law oversight in the European Union*.

Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 62ss.

Iorio, F. (2019). Opinion 1/17. Has the EU made peace with investment arbitration?. *International Business Law Journal*, 4 410ss.

Isiksel, T. (2016). *Europe's functional constitution. A theory of constitutionalism beyond the state*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Jacquè, J.P. (2011). The accession of the European Union to the European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. *Common Market Law Review*, 48 (4), 995, 1005.

Jacquè, J.P. (2014). CJUE-CEDH: 2-0. *Revue Trimestrielle de Droit Européen*, 40 (4), 823ss.

Jacquè, J.P. (2014). La Cour de Justice de l'Union et l'application de la Charte dans les Etats membres: "Mehr Licht". *European Yearbook on Human Rights*, 14, 125-147.

Jacquè, J.P. (2018). État de droit et confiance mutuelle. *Revue Trimestrielle de Droit Européen*, 54(2), 242ss.

Jakab, A., Kochenov, D. (2017). *The enforcement of EU law and values: Ensuring member states' compliance*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Jan Kuijper, P., Amtenbrink, F., Curtin, D., De Witte, B., McDonnell, A. (2018). *The law of the European Union and the European Communities*. Kluwer Law International, New York.

Janssens, C. (2013). *The principle of mutual recognition in*

European Union law. Oxford University Press, pp. 208ss.

Jarass, H.P. (2020). *Charta der Grundrecht der Europäischen Union: GRCh*. C.H. Beck, München.

Kelemen, D., Pech, L. (2018). Why autocrats love constitutional identity and constitutional pluralism. Reconnect Working paper, n. 2:

<https://reconnect-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/RECONNECT-WorkingPaper2-Kelemen-Pech-LP-KO.pdf>

Kelemen, D., Pech, L. (2019). The uses and abuses of constitutional pluralism: Undermining the rule of law in the name of constitutional identity in Hungary and Poland. *Cambridge Yearbook of European Legal Studies*, 21, 62ss.

Kellerbauer, M., Klamert, M., Tomkin, J. (2019). *Commentary on the European Union treaties and the Charter of fundamental rights*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Klamert, M. (2014). *The principle of loyalty in EU law*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 5ss.

Klamert, M. (2017). The autonomy of the EU (and of EU law): Through the kaleidoscope. *European Law Review*, 47, 816ss.

Kochenov, D. (2012). The application of EU law in the EU's overseas regions countries and territories after the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon. *Michigan State International Law Review*, 20 (3), 676ss.

Kochenov, D. (2015). Biting intergovernmentalism: The case

for the reinvention of Article 259 TFEU to make it a viable rule of law enforcement tool. *Hague Journal on the Rule of Law*, 7, 154ss.

Konstantinides, T. (2011). Constitutional identity as a shield and as a sword: The European legal order within the framework of national constitutional settlement. *Cambridge Yearbook of European Legal Studies*, 13.

Korenica, F. (2015). *The EU accession to the ECHR: Between Luxembourg's search for autonomy and Strasbourg's credibility on human rights protection*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 282ss.

Koutrakos, P., Nic Schuibhne, N., Syrpis, P. (2016). *Exceptions form EU free movement law: Derogation, justification and proportionality*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York.

Krenn, C. (2015). Autonomy and effectiveness as common concerns: A path to ECHR accession after Opinion 2/13. *German Law Journal*, 16 (1), 147ss.

Kuijer, M. (2011). The accession of the European Union to the ECHR: A gift for ECHR's 60th anniversary or an unwelcome intruder at the party?. *Amsterdam Law Forum*, 4 (3), 17-32.

Kumm, M. (2005). The jurisprudence of constitutional conflict: Constitutional supremacy in Europe before and after the Constitutional Treaty. *European Law Journal*, 11, 262ss.

Küris, E. (2018). On the rule of law and the quality of the law: Reflections on the constitutional-turned-international judge.

- Teoria y Realidad Constitucional*, 42, 134ss.
- Ladenburger, C. (2011). Vers l'adhésion de l'Union européenne à la Convention européenne des droits de l'homme. *Revue Trimestrielle de Droit Européen*, 47 (1), 20-26.
- Lambrecht, S. (2015). The sting is in the Tail: CJEU Opinion 2/13 objects to draft agreement on accession of the EU to the European Convention on Human Rights. *European Human Rights Law Review*, 15 (1), 185ss.
- Lebrun, G. (2016). De l'utilité de l'article 47 de la Charte des droits fondamentaux de l'union européenne. *Revue Trimestrielle des Droits de l'Homme*, 106, 433ss.
- Lenaerts, K. (2015). The Court of Justice as the guarantor of the rule of law within the European Union. In G. De Baere, J. Wouters (eds). *The contribution of international and supranational Courts to the rule of law*. Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, 242-264.
- Lenaerts, K. (2017). La vie après l'avis: Exploring the principle of mutual (yet not blind) trust. *Common Market Law Review*, 54, 805-840.
- Lenaerts, K. (2019). Limits on limitations: The essence of fundamental rights in the European Union. *German Law Journal*, 20, 782ss.
- Lenaerts, K. (2019). The Court of Justice of the EU as the guardian of the authority of EU law: A networking exercise. In

- W. Heusel, J.P. Rageade. *The authority of EU law*. ed. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Lenaerts, K., Bonichot, J.C., Kanninen, H., Naômè, C., Pohjankowski, P. (2019). *An ever-changing Union? Perspectives on the future of EU law in honour of Allan Rosas*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York.
- Lenaerts, K., Maselis, I., Gutman, K. (2014). *EU procedural law*. Oxford University Press.
- Liakopoulos, D. (2012). Fair trial and European Arrest Warrant. Evolution of the european criminal law and protection of human rights. *International and European Union Legal Matters*.
- Liakopoulos, D. (2018a). *Brexit and European Arrest Warrant. The role of CJEU. International and European Union Legal Matters-working paper series*.
- Liakopoulos, D. (2018b). The influence of EU law on national civil procedural law: Towards the adoption of common minimum standards?-La influencia de la legislaciòn de la UE en el derecho procesal civil nacional: ¿hacia la adopciòn de normas minimas comunes?. *Revista General de Derecho Europeo*, n. 46.
- Liakopoulos, D. (2018c). International criminal justice and respect for the rule of law: The view of the EU. *Juris Gradibus*.
- Liakopoulos, D. (2019a). Brexit y orden de detenciòn europea. *Revista Derechos en Acciòn*, 12 (2), 514ss.

- Liakopoulos, D. (2019b). *European integration through member states' constitutional identity in EU law*. Maklu, Antwerp, Portland.
- Liakopoulos, D. (2019c). Respect of rule of law between “internal affairs” and the European Union. The case of Poland and Hungary as a political v. functional *raison d'être*. *Acta Universitatis Danubius. Relationes Internationales*, 12 (2).
- Liakopoulos, D. (2022). Poxit v. European Union. *UNIO European Union Law*, 8 (1), 14-31.
- Lindseth, P. (2018). The perils of as. If constitutionalism. *European Law Journal*, 22, 696ss.
- Limbach, K. (2015). *Uniformity of customs administration in the EU*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York, 141ss.
- Lock, T. (2010). The ECJ and the ECtHR: The Future Relationship between the Two European Courts. *The Law and Practice of International Courts and Tribunals*, 8, 375-398.
- Lock, T. (2015). The future of EU accession to the ECHR after Opinion 2/13: Is it still possible and is it still desirable?. *Edinburgh School of Law Research Paper Series*.
- Lyn Entrikin, J. (2019). Global judicial transparency norms: A peek behind the robes in a whole new world. A look at global “democratizing” trends in judicial opinion-issuing practices. *Washington University Global Studies Law Review*, 18, 56ss.
- Mader, O. (2019). Enforcement of European Union values as a

political endeavour: Constitutional pluralism and value homogeneity intimes of persistent challenges to the rule of law. *Hague Journal on the Rule of Law*, 11, 135ss.

Maduro, M.P., Wind, M. (2017). *The transformation of Europe: Twenty five years on*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Mak, C. (2012). Rights and remedies: Article 47 EUCFR and effective judicial protection in European private law matters. *Amsterdam Law School Research Paper No. 2012-88*. Centre for the Study of European Contract Law Working Paper Series No. 11.

Mangas Martín, A. (2018). *Tratado de la Unión Europea, Tratado de Funcionamiento*. ed. Marcial Pons, Madrid.

Mansell, D. (2011). The European arrest warrant: The role of Judges when human rights are at risk. *New Journal of European Criminal Law*, 2 (1), 133ss.

Martinico, G. (2013). *The tangled complexity of the EU constitutional process: The frustrating knot of Europe*. ed. Routledge, London & New York, 119ss.

Martucci, F. (2019). *Droit de l'Union européenne*. LGDG, Paris

Matthes, C.Y. (2022) Judges as activists: How polish judges mobilise to defend the rule of law. *East European Politics*, 38 (3), 479ss.

Meyer, J., (ed.). (2014). *Charta der Grundrechte der Europäischen Union*. ed. Nomos, Baden-Baden, 813-826.

- Monsenego, J. (2019). *International taxation in a changing landscape: Liber amicorum in honour of Bertil Wilman*. Kluwer Law International, New York.
- Morano-Foadi, S., Andreadakis, S. (2020). *Protection of fundamental rights in Europe: The challenge of integration*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 71ss.
- Morano-Foadi, S., Vickers, L., (eds.). (2015). *Fundamental Rights in the EU-A matter for two Courts*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Nagy, C. (2019). *Investment arbitration in Central and Eastern Europe. Law and practice*. Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham.
- Neframi, E. (2015). Principe de coopération loyale et principe d'attribution dans le cadre de la mise en œuvre du droit de l'Union. *Cahiers de Droit Européen*, 27, 223ss.
- Neuwahl, N., Kovacs, C. (2020). Hungary and the EU's rule of law protection. *Journal of European Integration*, 42.
- Niblock, R. (2016). Mutual recognition, mutual trust?: Detention conditions and deferring an EAW. *New Journal of European Criminal Law*, 24 (2), 250ss.
- Nicola, F., Davies, B. (2017). *European Union law stories*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Nowag, J. (2017). EU law, constitutional identity and human dignity: A toxic mix?. *Common Market Law Review*, 53, 1451ss.

O'Meara, N. (2011). A more secure Europe of rights? The European Court of Human Rights, the Court of Justice of the European Union and EU Accession to the ECHR. *German Law Journal*, 12, 1813-1832.

Oates, J.G. (2020). *Constituent power and the legitimacy of international organizations. The constitution of supranationalism*. ed. Routledge, London & New York.

Öhlinger, Y. (2014). Vorlagepflicht bei Verstoß eines nationalen Gesetzes gegen Artikel 47 GRCh-Anmerkungen. *Europäische Zeitschrift für Wirtschaftsrecht*, 25, 957ss.

Östlund, A. (2019). *Effectiveness versus procedural protection. Tensions triggered by the EU law mandate of ex officio review*. Nomos Verlag, Baden-Baden.

Pech, L. (2022). The rule of law as a well-established and well-defined principle of EU law. *Hague Journal on the Rule of Law*, 14, 116ss.

Peers, S. (2015). The EU's Accession to the ECHR: The dream becomes a nightmare. *German Law Journal*, 16, 213, 222.

Peers, S. et al. (eds.). (2021). *The EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, A Commentary*. Hart Publishing, Nomos, C.H. Beck, Oxford & Oregon, Portland.

Perju, V. (2018). On the (de-)fragmentation of statehood in Europe: Reflections on Ernst-Wolfgang Böckenförde's Work on European integration. *German Law Journal*, 19, 403, 411ss.

- Pertek, J. (2021). *Le renvoi préjudicieux*. ed. Larcier, Bruxelles.
- Petite, M. (2015). The battle over Strasbourg: The protection of human rights across Europe has suffered a setback, thanks to the Court of Justice of the European Union. *Competition Law Insight*, 10ss: <https://www.cliffordchance.com/briefings/2015/03/the-battle-over-strasbourg--the-protection-of-human-rights-across.html>
- Picod, F. (2015). La Cour de justice a dit non à l'adhésion de l'Union européenne à la Convention EDH. *La Semaine Juridique, Édition Générale*, 230, 234.
- Picod, F., Van Droogbenbroeck, S. (2018). *Charte des droits fondamentaux de l'Union européenne*. ed. Bruylant, Bruxelles, 142ss.
- Picod, F., Van Droogbenbroeck, S. (2020). *Charte des droits fondamentaux de l'Union européenne*. ed. Bruylant, Bruxelles.
- Pila, J., Torremans, P. (2019). *European intellectual property law*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 38ss.
- Planzer, S. (2014). *Empirical views on European gambling law and addiction*. ed. Springer, Berlin.
- Platon, S. (2019). Le Respect de L'Etat de Droit Dans l'Union Européenne: La Cour de Justice A la Rescousse?. *Revue des Droits et Libertés Fondamentaux*, 36.
- Polakiewicz, J. (2013). EU law and the ECHR: Will the European Union's accession square the circle?. *European*

Human Rights Law Review, 6, 592-605.

Potteau, A. (2011). Quelle adhésion de l'Union Européenne à la CEDH pour quel niveau de protection des droits et de l'autonomie de l'ordre juridique de l'UE?. *Revue Générale Droit International Public*, 115, 77-111.

Prechal, S., Van Roermund, B., Van Roermund, G. (2008). *The coherence of EU law: The search for unity in divergent concepts*. Oxford University Press, 203ss.

Prete, M. (2016). *Infringement proceedings in EU law*. Kluwer Law International, New York.

Rasmussen, M. (2014). Revolutionizing EU law: A history of the Van Gend en Loos judgment. *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, 12, 136, 140.

Rasmussen, M., Martinsen, D. (2019). EU constitutionalization revisited: Redressing a central assumption in European studies. *European Law Journal*, 25, 252ss.

Ravasi, E. (2017). *Human rights protection by the ECtHR and the ECJ: A comparative analysis in light of the equivalency doctrine*. ed. Brill, Bruxelles.

Reffel, C. (2019). The CETA opinion of the European Court of Justice and its implications. Not that selfish after all. *Journal of International Economic Law*, 22, 504ss.

Ripol Carulla, S., Ligartemendia Uceizabarrena, J.I. (2022). *La Carta de derechos fundamentales de la Unión Europea*. Marcial

Pons, Madrid.

Rizcallah, C. (2019). The challenges to trust-based governance in the EU: Assessing the use of mutual trust as a driver of EU integration. *European Law Journal*, 25 (1), 42ss.

Roccati, M. (2014). *Le rôle du juge national dans l'espace judiciaire européen du marché intérieur à la coopération civile*. ed. Larcier, Bruxelles.

Rodin, S. (2011). National identity and market freedoms after the Treaty of Lisbon. *Croatian Yearbook of European Law & Policy*, 7, 16ss.

Rodin, S., Perišin, T. (2015). *Judicial application of international law in Southeast Europe*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 8ss.

Roes, T. (2016). Limits to loyalty. The relevance of Article 4(3) TEU. *Cahiers de Droit Européen*, 52, 256ss.

Rosas, A., Armati, L. (2018). *EU constitutional law: An introduction*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York.

Rossi, L.S. (2015). Fundamental values, principle and rights after the Lisbon treaty: The long journey toward an European constitutional identity. In A.A.V.V. *Europe(s), Droit(s), européen(s), Liber Amicorum Vlad Constantinesco*. de. Bruylant, Bruxelles, 512ss.

Rossi, L.S. (2017). "Same legal value as the treaties?" Rank, primacy and direct effects of the EU Charter of fundamental rights. *German Law Journal*, 18 (4), 774ss.

- Rossi, L.S. (2017). The principle of equality among Member States of the European Union. In L.S. Rossi, F. Casolari (eds.), *The principle of equality in EU law*. ed Springer, Cham, 3-42.
- Rossi, L.S., Casolari, F. (2014). *The EU after lisbon: Amending or coping with the existing treaties?*. ed. Springer, Berlin.
- Saffian, M., Düsterhau, D. (2014). A Union of effective judicial protection: Addressing a multi-level challenge through the lens of article 47 CFREU. *Yearbook of European Law*, 33 (1), 3ss.
- Saiz Arnaiz, A., Alcoberro Llivina, C. (2013). Introduction: Why constitutional identity suddenly matters: A tale of brave states, a mighty Union and the decline of sovereignty. In A. Saiz Arnaiz, C. Alcoberro Llivina (eds.). *National constitutional identity and European integration*. ed. Intersentia, Antwerp, Oxford, 4ss.
- Sankari, S. (2016). *The many constitutions of Europe*. ed. Routledge, London & New York.
- Scheppele, K.L., Vladimirovich Kochenov, D., Grabowska-Moroz, B. (2020). EU values are law, after all: Enforcing EU values through systemic infringement actions by the European Commission and the Member States of the European Union. *Yearbook of European Law*, 39, 6ss.
- Schmahl, S. (2019). *The national identity criterion in the crossfire between European integration and the preservation of national sovereignty*. ed. Springer, Berlin.

- Schmidt, M. (2018). The infringement procedure in the rule of law crisis: How to make effective use of article 258 TFEU. *Common Market Law Review*, 55 (4), 1061-1065.
- Scholten, M., Brenninkmeijer, A. (2020). *Controlling EU Agencies: The rule of law in a multi-jurisdictional legal order*. Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham, 95ss.
- Schütze, R., Tridimas, T. (2018). *Oxford principles of European Union law*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Schwarze, J., Becker, V., Hatje, A., Schoo, J. (2019). *EU-Kommentar*. ed. Nomos, Baden-Baden.
- Smith, E. (2013). Running before we can walk? Mutual recognition at the expense of fair trials in Europe's Area of Freedom, Justice and Security. *New Journal of European Criminal Law*, 3 (1), 82ss.
- Smith, M. (2015). The evolution of infringement and sanction procedures. In D. Chalmers, A. Arnall (eds). *The oxford handbook of European Union law*. Oxford University Press, 2015, pp. 376ss.
- Soloch, P. (2019). CJEU Judgment in case C-294/16 Achmea: Single decision and its multi-faced fallout. *The Law & Practice of International Courts and Tribunals*, 18 (1).
- Sousa Ferro, M. (2019). *Market definition in EU competition law*. Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham.
- Spaventa, E. (2015). A very fearful Court? The protection of

fundamental rights in the European Union after Opinion 2/13. *Maastricht Journal of European and Comparative Law*, 22, 51ss.

Spieker, L.D. (2018). Framing and managing constitutional identity conflicts: How to stabilize the modus vivendi between the Court of Justice and national constitutional Courts'. *Common Market Law Review*, 38, 387ss.

Spieker, L.D. (2019). Breathing life into the Union's common values: On the judicial application of article 2 TEU in the EU value crisis. *German Law Journal*, 20, 1188ss.

Spieker, L.D. (2021). Defending Union values in judicial proceedings. On how to turn article 2 TEU into a judicially applicable provision. In A. Von Bogdandy, P. Bogdanowicz, I. Canor, C. Grabenwarter, M. Taborowski, M. Schmidt (eds). *Defending checks and balances in EU Member States*. Beiträge zum ausländischen öffentlichen Recht und Völkerrecht, vol. 298. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

Stein, E. (1981). Lawyers, judges and the making of the transnational constitution. *American Journal of International Law*, 75.

Stern, K., Sachs, M. (2016). *Europäische Grundrecht Charta*. ed. C.H. Beck, München, 75ss.

Storskrubb, E. (2018). Mutual trust and the dark horse of civil justice. *Cambridge Yearbook of European Legal Studies*, 20,

184ss.

Sudre, F. (2021). *La Convention européenne des droits de l'homme*. PUF, Paris.

Swoboda, S. (2015). The self-perception of the European Court of Justice and its neglect of the defense perspective in its preliminary rulings on judicial cooperation in criminal matters: A small note on a fundamental misunderstanding. *Zeitschrift für Internationale Strafrechtsdogmatik*, 10 (7-8), 361ss.

Sybesma-Knol, N. (2014). The European system for the promotion and protection of human rights. *Georgia Journal of International & Comparative Law*, 20.

Terhechte, J.P. (2012). Judicial accountability and public liability. The german “judges privilege” under the influence of European and international law. *German Law Journal*, 13 (3), 317ss.

Tinière, R., Vial, C. (2020). *Les dix ans de la Charte des droits fondamentaux e l'Union européenne*. ed. Larcier, Bruxelles.

Tinsley, A. (2013). Protecting criminal defence rights through EU Law: Opportunities and challenges. *New Journal of European Criminal Law*, 3 (3), 461ss.

Tomljenović, V., Bobiroga-Vukobrat, N., Butorac Malnar, V., Kunda, I. (2017). *EU competition and state aid rules: Public and private enforcement*. ed. Springer, Berlin.

Toniatti, R. (2013). Sovereignty lost, constitutional identity

- regained. In A. Saiz Arnaiz, C. Alcoberro Llivina (eds.). *National constitutional identity and European integration*. ed. Intersentia, Antwerp, Oxford, 49ss.
- Torres Perez, A. (2013). Too many voices? The prior involvement of the Court of Justice of the European Union?. *European Journal of Human Rights*, 40, 565-583.
- Usherwood, J., Pinder, S. (2018). *The European Union. A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Uzelac, A., Hendrik, C., Van Rhee, R. (2018). *Transformation on civil justice. Unity and diversity*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 304ss.
- Van Raepenbusch, S. (2016). *Droit institutionnel de l'Union européenne*. ed. Larcier, Bruxelles.
- Van Rossem, J.W. (2013). The autonomy of EU law: More is less?. In R.A. Wessel, S. Blockmans (eds). *Between autonomy and dependence: The EU legal order under the influence of International Organisations*. TMC Asser Press, The Hague.
- Varju, M. (2014). *European Union human rights law: The dynamics of interpretation and context*. Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham, 174ss.
- Varju, M. (2019). *Between compliance and particularism. Member State interests and EU law*. ed. Springer, Berlin, 162ss.
- Varju, M. (2019). *Member State interests and EU law: Revisiting the foundations of member state obligations*. ed. Routledge, London/New York .

- Vauchez, A. (2010). The transnational politics of judicialization. Van Gend en Loos and the making of EU polity. *European Law Journal*, 16, 7ss.
- Veenbrink, M. (2019). *Criminal law principles and the enforcement of EU and national competition law: A silent takeover?*. Kluwer Law International, New York.
- Vervaele, A.E. (2015) Mutual legal assistance in criminal matters to control (transnational) criminality. In N. Boister, R.J. Currie (eds). *Handbook of transnational criminal law*. ed. Routledge, London & New York, 123ss.
- Villiger, M.E. (2023). *Handbook on the European Convention on Human Rights*. Brill, Bruxelles.
- Virseda Fernández, C. (2020). *Unión europea*. Editorial Aranzadi, Pamplona.
- Voenny, S., Neuman, J.L., (eds.). (2018). *Human rights, democracy and legitimacy in a world disorder*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Vogener, S., Weathrill, S. (2017). *General principles of law: European and comparative perspectives*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York, 31ss.
- Von Bogdandy, A., Schill, S. (2011). Overcoming absolute primacy: Respect for national identity, under the Lisbon Treaty. *Common Market Law Review*, 48 (5), 1417-1453.
- Wallace, H.S., Pollack, M.A., Young, A.R. (2010). *Policy*

making in the European Union. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 139ss.

Weiler, J. (1991). The transformation of Europe. *Yale Law Journal*, 100, 2403ss, 2425-2426.

Wendt, I.E. (2012). *EU competition law and liberal professions: An uneasy relationship?*. Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, The Hague, 312ss.

Wessel, R.A., Łazowski, A. (2015). When Caveats Turn into Locks: Opinion 2/13 on Accession of the European Union to the ECHR. *German Law Journal*, 16, 179ss.

Woods, L., Watson, P. (2017). *Steiner & Woods European Union law*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 37ss.

Wouters, J., Rynbgaert, C., Ruys, T., De Baere, G. (2018). *International law: A european perspective*. Bloomsbury Publishing, New York.